

How come the quantum?

Testing the topological origin of Planck's quantum of action

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Abstract

An answer to Wheeler's question "How come the quantum?" is proposed. Our answer goes back to an approach by Dirac and proposes a topological origin for Planck's quantum of action. We propose a new fundamental principle: the quantum of action \hbar is due to twist-induced switches of crossings among fluctuating strands of Planck radius embedded in three dimensions. Due to their small radius, strands are invisible, though physically real. Nevertheless, crossing switches due to Dirac's trick couple to photons, are thus observable, and define all physical observables. We verify the consequences of this fundamental principle against the basic quantum effects. The principle yields the appearance of particles as rational tangles of strands, their indistinguishability, spin, and statistics. The principle also yields the quantization of action and of angular momentum, wave-particle duality, emergence of wave functions and Hilbert spaces, interference, Feynman's path integral formulation, the Schrödinger equation, Heisenberg's indeterminacy relation, non-commutativity, entanglement, the properties of photons, probabilities in measurements, Born's rule, decoherence, spinors, chirality, antiparticles, and the Dirac equation. Strands also yield the principle of least action. The topological origin of the quantum of action appears to agree with all observations and to be unique. Strands go beyond quantum mechanics: they determine lepton masses, solve the mass hierarchy problem, and are consistent with the properties of physical space, with quantum field theory, particle physics, and general relativity.

Keywords: origin of Planck's quantum of action; origin of quantum theory; origin of wave functions; origin of the principle of least action; origin of particle mass.

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1 The challenge of Wheeler’s question

In an essay published in 1986, Wheeler wrote [1]:

It will surely not be by asking always small questions that the community will some day find the answer to the great question, “How come the quantum?” To ask the right question, however, one must have, as is well known, some glimmer of the answer. It is also old experience that in order to break out of blank puzzlement and into the right question-and-answer circuit, one must try and try again. One must, if necessary, make a fool of oneself many times over [...]

In other words, Wheeler asked with his characteristic intensity: how does the smallest observable action value, Planck’s quantum of action \hbar [2–4], arise in nature?

The proposal that we make in this paper is to take seriously the geometric and topological content of *Dirac's trick*. Dirac observed that if each localized particle is visualized as attached by tethers to its surroundings – for example, to a distant chair or to a large sphere surrounding the laboratory, such as the cosmological horizon – then a 2π turn of the particle does not bring it and its tethers back to the original position, but that a 4π turn does bring everything – particle and tethers – back to the original position. The first figures in this text illustrate the observation. Dirac suggested this as a topological-geometrical model for spinors and spin states of fermions, as told in Section 2. Dirac did not intend that one should think of all particles as connected by invisible tethers to their surroundings, yet that is our proposal! Section 3 motivates this proposal further.

The usual approach to Dirac's trick is to point out that it can be seen as a visualization of the homotopy properties – i.e., the deformation properties – of the rotation group of three-space $SO(3)$ and its relationship with the double covering of $SO(3)$ by the unitary group $SU(2)$, which has the topology of a three-dimensional sphere S^3 . In this usual approach, the full turn of a fermion creates a new state because the rotation yields a *lifting* to the double cover $SU(2)$, and that this lifting is necessary because quantum processes must be unitary, as told in Section 4. This means that we create a model of the world in which particles, quantum phenomena, and empty space are composed of invisible strands. In particular, we will show that strands, together with Dirac's trick, lead to a fundamental principle that implies and yields standard quantum mechanics. Elementary particles will correspond to simple tangles, as expanded in Section 5. In the course of this creation, we indicate many projects that beg for more investigation and further construction, both mathematical and physical. Thus we ask the reader to study this paper as a proposal for the growing of a new theory in which these invisible strands take a central role.

Standard quantum mechanics arose once Planck discovered that the explanation of blackbody radiation required the introduction of the quantum of action $h = 2\pi\hbar$. De Broglie's discovery of the role of \hbar in matter waves was followed by Heisenberg's result that quantum observables do not commute, and that \hbar enters their evolution. As a consequence of the work by Schrödinger, standard quantum mechanics is based on three ideas. First, the physical state is a vector in a complex Hilbert space. Second, the evolution of a system, thus every physical process not involving measurements or observations, is a unitary transformation, a unitary operator, in the system's Hilbert space. Third, every measurement or observation follows Born's rule: the measured results are obtained by taking the absolute square of the coefficient of some projection of the state vector. The three ideas contain no interpretation of \hbar , except as an element of discreteness that makes the description of quantum systems work. In the following, we are suggesting a fundamental relationship of \hbar with the nature of space itself via Dirac's trick – also called the orientation entanglement relation – and more simply, via a crossing switch. As a result of taking this way of thinking seriously, we propose many detailed visualizations in quantum mechanics. These visualizations are an invitation to the reader to engage in inner and outer discussions about this way of modeling nature.

We will show how standard quantum mechanics can be visualized in terms of a geometric model of strands in three-dimensional space. This includes the quantum of action and the quantization of angular momentum presented in Section 6. Spinning particles are visualized as rotating tangles of strands that continuously perform Dirac's trick. Rotating tangles of strands allow visualizing wave functions, as told in Section 7, and studying both the mathematical and the physical aspects of superpositions, as told in Section 8. The strand model is a hidden variable model

with a rich hidden and contextual structure that, however, remains completely *equivalent* to standard quantum theory, because only crossing switches due to Dirac's trick are observable in the strand model. Wave-particle duality then arises from strands automatically. Planck's relation and de Broglie's relation are deduced in Section 9.

Standard quantum mechanics is recovered from strands. We will show that rotating tangles that continuously perform Dirac's trick explain particle spin, statistics, and wave-particle duality. We can also use strand tangles performing Dirac's trick to formulate the Feynman path integral description for wave functions, with a geometric interpretation for the evolving phase along a path and with a geometric interpretation for the appearance of the action in relation to the phase. Section 10 presents this point of view. It yields the Schrödinger equation. Orbitals, quantum jumps, operators, non-commutativity, entanglement, photons, decoherence, indeterminacy, the Dirac equation, and the principle of least action are deduced from strands in the sections up to Section 19. In simple words, *Dirac's trick yields all of quantum mechanics*.

The remaining sections first deduce experimental tests of crossing switches, explore alternative models, and investigate arguments against crossing switches. Dirac's trick will also lead us *beyond* quantum mechanics: in the case of leptons, Dirac's trick allows the estimation of their mass values and the explanation of the validity of the equivalence principle, while tangles and untangled strands yield quantum field theory, general relativity and consequences for the foundations of physics.

The visualization of \hbar with strands is a simple proposal for an interpretation of quantum mechanics that also allows exploring questions about nature that are still unanswered, for example in the domains of quantum gravity and cosmology. Different opinions of the authors on various issues are pointed out. Thus, the present paper should be seen both as foundational and developmental for fundamental physics.

Despite the incisiveness of Wheeler's question about the origin of "the quantum", the research literature offers only rare answers. Indeed, several issues that have hampered the investigation in the past appear to be solved only by the strand model. The habit of calling \hbar "Planck's constant" has encouraged ignoring Wheeler's question and avoiding searching for a visualization. In contrast, strands allow a clear definition and visualization of "the quantum".

The quantum of action \hbar is the reason that blackbody radiation is made of photons and that light produces the photoelectric effect. It has been an open challenge to provide a visualization of photons that agrees with all observations, including the quantum of action. The strand proposal for the photon, its properties, and its interference behavior is presented in Section 16.

The quantum of action \hbar describes wave-particle duality. Explaining and visualizing wave functions and superpositions is difficult. Although visualizations as a complex function are available, such as those by Thaller [5, 6], *none* incorporates or visualizes Planck's constant \hbar . There is a widespread conviction that wave functions, superpositions, and the mathematical structure of quantum mechanics *cannot* be visualized in all their aspects, and surely *not* in three dimensions for multiple particles. In contrast, strands do allow visualizing wave functions and Hilbert spaces, allow this in three spatial dimensions, and even allow this visualization for many particles.

There has been a vague suspicion that the quantum of action \hbar might be related to some kind of discreteness of physical space or even of nature itself. However, there is no accepted solution for this issue. Deducing the origin of \hbar requires understanding how physical continuity arises from an underlying and hidden kind of partial discreteness. As long as observables are assumed to be

Figure 1: In his lectures, Dirac demonstrated the properties of spin $\hbar/2$, a pure quantum effect, using a pair of scissors tethered to a chair. Any object with at least three tethers, such as the illustrated pair of scissors, can return to its original state by untangling its tethers only after a double rotation, but not after a single rotation. Tethered objects and spin $\hbar/2$ particles thus behave similarly.

continuous, deducing the origin of \hbar appears impossible. In contrast, strands yield the emergence of all continuous observables.

Finally, all senses, all observations, and all measurement apparatuses make use of \hbar . Also the definitions of all SI units are based, directly or indirectly, on \hbar . Without a description of the origin or a visualization of \hbar , quantum measurements cannot be described. In contrast, in the strand model of nature, quantum jumps appear as crossing switches, as told in Section 12. Section 15 explains entanglement with strands. As a consequence, strands allow a description of decoherence and the quantum measurement process. Section 16 does so for the observations of photons. Section 17 describes measurements in the wave function picture, including decoherence and collapse, and in Feynman's path integral formulation. Also gauge theory and gravity are briefly described. Strands imply that all observations are due to the Dirac trick and the Planck-scale geometry of space.

In short, we envisage a world of strands that is very much like the physical world that we do observe, but with strands that are *invisible* and *fluctuating*. Switches of strands due to the Dirac trick are observable, however, and this is the extra relationship connecting the strand world to our usual world. Assuming this connection and assuming that the physics of the strand space is similar to physics already known, we embark on the explanation of quantum phenomena. A moving and spinning particle tangle will need the Dirac trick [7] to happen for its motion to be unimpeded. We will describe its motion based on the density of crossings and the density of Dirac tricks. The assumptions of the strand model, condensed in the fundamental principle, are both *simple* – invisible strands, existence of Dirac's trick, and deformations, or isotopies, of strands that cannot pass through one another – and *involved*, in that we will use background physical ideas from our everyday three-dimensional world. This mix of assumptions allows us to explore the physics of the strand world and to develop a picture of how physics works from this point of view.

2 The arguments leading to identify \hbar with twist-induced crossing switches

From 1929 onward, in his lectures on quantum theory, Dirac used *tethers* to demonstrate the properties of matter particles [9, 10].

Figure 2: A simplified version of Dirac's trick shows that keeping the scissors fixed, a twist by $+2\pi$ is equivalent to a twist by -2π . This implies that a twist by $+4\pi$ is equivalent to no twist. This equivalence is illustrated further in the next two figures.

Definition 1: The observation of Figure 1, Figure 2 or Figure 3 – a tethered rotation by 4π is equivalent, via strand shape deformations or fluctuations, to no rotation at all – is called *Dirac's trick* in the following.

Following Dirac, we imagine that all matter particles are *tethered*, i.e., *anchored* to the cosmological horizon – the black night sky – by *unobservable strands*. He modeled matter particles with scissors and the cosmological horizon with a chair. Rotating the scissors by 2π around any axis leads to tangled tethers, whereas rotating the scissors by 4π enables untangling the tethers. A tethered rotation by 4π is thus *equivalent* to no rotation at all, in contrast to a rotation by 2π . Tethers thus reproduce the observed unusual behavior of the spin $\hbar/2$ of matter particles. This equivalence also applies if the tethers depart towards several chairs or in completely different directions.

In physics, it is common to abbreviate spin $\hbar/2$ as spin $1/2$. The present article uses the longer notation to enable better checks of the answer to Wheeler's question. Indeed, one of the first tasks will be to clarify how Dirac related the rotation of tethered scissors to the quantum of action \hbar .

The key to Dirac's trick is shown in Figure 2 using a simplified set-up. Note that the scissors are *not moved* during the process, which shows that a twist in the tethers by $+2\pi$ is equivalent to a twist by -2π . As a result, a twist by $+4\pi$ is equivalent to two twists by $+2\pi$ and again $+2\pi$,

Dirac's trick: under rotation, *tethered* structures behave as spin $\hbar/2$ particles

Dirac's trick: under rotation, also structures *connected with belts* behave as spin $\hbar/2$ particles

Figure 3: Any structure, including the depicted *tangle core*, connected to the cosmological horizon with three or more *tethers* (top) or with one or more *belts* (bottom) behaves as a *spin $\hbar/2$ particle*: it can return to the original situation *only* after a rotation by 4π . For animated versions, see vimeo.com/62228139 or motionmountain.net/videos.html#strands. Dirac's trick works for arbitrarily large numbers of tethers or belts, and independently of their observability, unobservability, or distribution in space. In particular, Dirac's trick shows that tethered structures can *rotate continuously*. *Tethers model and visualize spin $\hbar/2$* .

The fermion trick: under exchange, *tethered* structures behave as fermions

The fermion trick with belts: again, under exchange, structures *connected by belts* behave as fermions

Figure 4: Pairs of *tangle cores* with three or more tethers (top), or with one or more belts (bottom), behave as *fermions*: they return to the original situation *only* after a double exchange. This *fermion trick* works for arbitrarily large numbers of tethers or belts, independently of their observability, unobservability, or distribution in space. The fermion trick also works if, in addition, any number of tethers or belts connect the two cores directly to each other [8]. (For a proof, it is sufficient to imagine stretching the direct connections by pulling the midpoint to a large distance.) The fermion trick is equivalent to Dirac's trick. In particular, the fermion trick shows that tethered structures can orbit each other continuously. *Tethers model and visualize fermions.*

Figure 5: The fermion behavior of matter particles – double exchange is equivalent to no exchange – can be experienced in animations, such as the one produced by Antonio Martos de la Torre. For the actual animated version, see vimeo.com/62143283 or motionmountain.net/videos.html#strands.

and thus to twists by $+2\pi$ and -2π , and thus to no twist at all. Figure 2 thus means that a twist by 4π corresponds to the identity operator, a twist by $\pm 2\pi$ corresponds to -1 , and a twist by π is an order 4 operator corresponding to $\sqrt{-1}$. Because experiments can observe particle rotations or exchanges, in the strand world, even though strands are *unobservable*, we assume that $\pm 2\pi$ twists are *observable*. It will become clear that, mathematically, twists realize a double covering of the usual $SO(3)$ rotation group. This means that we identify the basic quantum process as the lift between one sheet and the other sheet in the double covering $SU(2) = S^3 \rightarrow SO(3)$. Such lifts correspond directly to twist transitions and to unitary evolutions via $SU(2)$ that in turn correspond to rotations of 3-space mediated by the rotation group $SO(3)$. Quantum evolutions correspond to unitary evolutions, and so the observable events of the strand world correspond to fundamental observables in the quantum world. Strands thus explain, through the relation between rotations, twists, and $i = \sqrt{-1}$, why quantum mechanics requires complex numbers.

In the following, *both* tethers *and* particles are assumed to consist of unobservable strands. This assumption will be confirmed in the following. Figure 3 presents a schematic version of Dirac's demonstration that uses strands to model both tethers and particles. Since all physical systems in the strand world are tangles, we can examine them via Dirac's trick or via the relationship

The fundamental principle of the strand tangle model

Strand description: Planck's quantum of action \hbar is due to *observable* crossing switches of *unobservable* strands of Planck radius

Resulting observation:

Figure 6: The *fundamental principle* extracted from Dirac's trick and the fermion trick is illustrated. It forms the *only assumption* of the strand tangle model. The quantum of action \hbar results from a localized, twist-induced *strand crossing switch*, i.e., from the change of which strand passes above the other at a position in three-dimensional space. The crossing switch is the simplest *observable* process in nature: it describes an *event* and defines \hbar as the unit of the physical action W . An event is an *effectively point-like* process because its double Planck time duration and the Planck radius of the fluctuating strands are usually negligible. These unattainably small scales make strands *unobservable* and limit measurement accuracy to two Planck lengths and two Planck times. In nature, *all* quantum processes, *all* observations and *all* processes consist of crossing switches.

between the rotation group and its unitary covering. It will be shown that the quantum of action \hbar is intimately related to unitary evolution.

Figure 4 and Figure 5 show that tethers also yield *fermion behavior*: two tethered matter particles after a single exchange *differ* from a double exchange, which is equivalent to no exchange.

Definition 2: The tether behavior of Figure 4 and Figure 5, showing that double matter particle exchange is equivalent to no exchange at all, is called the *fermion trick*.

Dirac's trick and the fermion trick imply each other: they are equivalent. Strands thus imply the spin-statistics theorem for fermions. Despite the elegance of his tether model, Dirac never published anything about it. Nonetheless, through his lectures, the tether model became known throughout the world, because all observations confirm that all matter particles are fermions, and vice versa. A precise description of both tricks requires

Definition 3: A *strand* is an infinitely flexible, infinitely twistable, impenetrable, smooth (infinitely differentiable) curve *without* ends, intersections, branches, or knots, *with* an unobservable small radius, that *fluctuates* in 3d space.

Definition 4: A *shape fluctuation* is any smooth strand deformation or isotopy.

Definition 5: A *crossing* is the region of the locally shortest distance between two strand segments that are not parallel and not lying in a common plane. It is observer-invariant.

The definition of crossing differs from the one used in graph theory and in topology: in the present context, a crossing is always *skew* and defined *independently* of any projection.

Definition 6: The *position* of a crossing is the midpoint of the shortest distance between the strands.

Definition 7: A *crossing switch* is the *twist-induced* process, at a given point in space, illus-

Why crossing switches are observable:

The first and the last state can be distinguished in experiments

Figure 7: In nature and in quantum theory, a phase change by 2π of a fermion is observable because it changes the sign of the wave function. In the strand tangle model, crossing switches, shown by the dotted circles, are the only difference between a fermion before and after rotation by 2π . Therefore, crossing switches mediated by twists must be observable processes, *even* if the strands themselves are unobservable.

trated in Figure 6. It is observer-invariant.

Due to the required twist, the concept of a crossing switch used here *differs* from the concept used in topology, which is best described as ‘cut and reconnect’. In nature and in the strand model, crossing switches *cannot* occur via cutting, reconnection, or via interpenetration of strands because these processes would contradict the observed difference between one and two rotations, would contradict the requirement of continuity, would contradict, as explained later, the minimum length in nature, and would contradict many observations about particle physics and gravitation.

In nature, interference experiments show that the change of sign of a wave function is observable. Wave functions change sign whenever quantum matter particles rotate by 2π . Figure 7 illustrates that crossing switches are the only difference between an unrotated tethered matter particle and one rotated by 2π . Therefore, to produce a realistic description of nature in agreement with observations, the model requires

Definition 8: Crossing switches are *observable*. Strands are *unobservable*.

The origin of these seemingly paradoxical definitions – the first due to the coupling of crossing switches to photons and the second due to the unattainability of the minimum length $\sqrt{4G\hbar/c^3}$ – and their complete agreement with observations will be presented in the following. Strand behavior thus differs from that of ropes in everyday life. Strand behavior also differs from that of deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) in living cells, where crossing switches are usually not observable, whereas strands are [11]. But strand crossing switches and Dirac’s trick have further consequences.

The minimum number of crossing switches needed to observe a rotated particle

Figure 8: To observe a particle rotation by 2π – a boson in this case – *one* crossing switch is the minimum necessary number. A crossing switch, shown by the dotted circle, thus corresponds to \hbar . A crossing switch is thus an observable discrete change resulting from unobservable continuous processes.

In 1980, decades after Dirac but still before Wheeler’s essay, Battey-Pratt and Racey started with Dirac’s description of particles as objects tethered with unobservable, flexible, twistable, fluctuating strands and *generalized* it. Instead of describing only fermion rotations and exchanges, they described *all* their types of motion [12]: they derived all of relativistic quantum mechanics, including the Klein-Gordon equation and the Dirac equation, by combining Dirac’s trick and special relativity. Alas, when they wrote to Dirac about their result, they received no response.

To clarify the effect of tethers and to answer Wheeler’s question, the start is provided by

Observation O1: All change and all motion in nature is observed to consist of evolving *localized particles*, evolving *two-dimensional horizons*, and evolving *three-dimensional empty space*.

In the following, we are mainly concerned with the motion of particles, and mention black hole horizons and general relativity only in passing. Motion is described with observables. The most important observable is given by

Definition 10: (Physical) *action*, the observer-invariant scalar measuring the change in a physical system, is the observable with the unit of energy times time.

In the usual description of motion, the action is the integral over the Lagrangian density and provides the starting point of the precise description of motion [13]. We do not need this starting point here, because we will *derive* the central role of action later on, in Section 19. Instead, here we start with one of the observational limits of nature.

In nature, in 1899 [2], Planck was the first to make the

Observation O2a: The smallest observable action value is Planck’s quantum of action \hbar .

Planck’s discovery led to quantum mechanics, quantum theory, and quantum field theory [3]. The *complete* observation O2, with all other limits observed in nature, is given in the [Appendix](#). It clarifies that the observed limits and the observed types of evolution just mentioned form the only two assumptions of the strand model, and that these two observations appear to imply that nature consists of strands.

Tangle and hand rotations by π behave like the *unit quaternions* and do not commute

Figure 9: Both strands and a right human hand illustrate the relation between rotations by π and the unit quaternions, including their non-commutativity.

Combining the smallest observable action with Figure 7 and Figure 8 leads to a result that was first proposed in 1987 [14, 15]. By analyzing Dirac's trick, in order to describe the physical, observable consequences of unobservable tethers in a precise manner, Kauffman formulated the

Fundamental principle: Planck's *quantum of action* \hbar is due to a twist-induced *crossing switch* of unobservable strands, the process depicted in Figure 6.

The fundamental principle condenses all assumptions so far by modeling the quantum of action \hbar as the exchange between a strand underpass and an overpass at a given position in space. In simple words, *every crossing switch produces a quantum of action \hbar* . As will be shown in the following, this description of \hbar , combining *topology* and *geometry*, answers Wheeler's question about the origin of the quantum because modeling \hbar with a crossing switch of unobservable strands describes *all* situations in which \hbar arises in nature.

Thesis 12: All quantum effects are due to crossing switches.

Kauffman's inspiration for the fundamental principle modeling \hbar was Conway's *skein relation* that is used to describe topological knot invariants, although the switching in the skein relation is usually interpreted differently. Knot invariants can be used to distinguish tangled and untangled situations. In addition, the skein relation expresses the non-commutation of topological operations.

Figure 10: Another way to illustrate the relation between the unit quaternions and a right hand.

Likewise, a topological and non-commutative structure arises in Penrose's binor calculus and in spin networks [16, 17], which can be modeled with strands. A further argument leading to the principle was the analogy between topological operations on links and Lie algebras [15], and between topological operations and the Dirac algebra [18]. Above all, Dirac's trick for a tethered object, such as a tangle, is related to the non-commutation of its rotations and, therefore, to the algebra of the unit *quaternions* [12, 15]. The three rotations of a tangle core by π along the three coordinate axes behave like the unit quaternions i, j, k : Dirac's trick yields $i^4 = 1, i^2 = -1$ and the same result for j and k , as illustrated in Figure 9 for strands and for a right human hand. In this equivalence, 1 corresponds to no rotation at all. Playing with tangle cores directly yields $ij = k, ji = -k$, all the other binary products, and the well-known triple product $ijk = -1$, which is illustrated with a right hand in Figure 10. Concatenations of tangle core rotations by π thus behave like the products of unit quaternions, including their non-commutativity. This leads to

Thesis 13: Strand topology, non-commutativity, and quantum effects go hand in hand.

Also this thesis will be confirmed in this article. On the one hand, strand topology yields non-commutativity, including a visualization of $SU(2)$ and spin behavior. On the other hand, this result suggests that the non-commutative behavior of quantum particles has a topological origin. In nature and in quantum physics, non-commutativity is always expressed with Planck's quantum of action \hbar . It is thus natural to associate \hbar to strands, as is done in the fundamental principle.

Note 14: To highlight the flow of arguments in the strand model and to facilitate criticism and potential falsification, each intermediate result is marked in bold, usually as **Statement**.

In nature, physical action measures the *change* in a system. All observations detect change. However, action values smaller than \hbar are not observable. The fundamental principle thus implies

Statement 15: A crossing switch is the *quantum of change* in nature.

Statement 16: A crossing switch is an *elementary process* in nature.

Statement 17: All observations are *due to* and *composed of* crossing switches.

Equivalently, strands confirm that changes smaller than \hbar are *not* observable and that the quantum of action \hbar plays a role in every elementary process, and thus in every process and in every

observation. These consequences can be summarized as

Thesis 18: Nature – particles, space, horizons – *consists of* unobservable strands with observable crossing switches.

This thesis agrees with all experiments and observations, as will become clear in the text.

In nature, the quantum of action \hbar is also the unit of *orbital* angular momentum. The reason is the definition of angular momentum as *action per full rotation*. Thus, the smallest observable action implies the smallest orbital angular momentum \hbar . Figure 8 shows that strands confirm the result. Then, a century ago, the discovery of spin required clarification. Each elementary fermion returns to itself after a rotation by 4π . The spin value is given by the smallest observable action \hbar divided by the number of full rotations needed to return to itself. This yields

Statement 19: Every *tethered* elementary fermion has the spin value $\hbar/2$.

Figure 7 is Dirac's explanation of fermion spin [9]. Tethers thus imply that the spin of elementary particles is *independent* of the rotation frequency, of the size, and of the mass of the rotating elementary particle, a result that has not been explained otherwise in the literature. Tethers thus show that even though the smallest observable action value is \hbar , a spin value $\hbar/2$ is possible. Indeed, all experiments confirming a spin value $\hbar/2$ require a spin flip, i.e., a change of spin orientation along an axis from $\hbar/2$ to $-\hbar/2$. Such a spin flip corresponds to an observable action \hbar . As Dirac explained to Gardner [9], tethers further visualize that a spin value smaller than $\hbar/2$ is impossible. All these properties of spin are observed. Only the strands and tethers are not.

Despite various attempts [19, 20], the research literature contains no alternative model of \hbar agreeing with observations. Also the publications that cite Wheeler's question, such as references [21–27], propose no model for \hbar . The reasons for this lack of alternatives will become clear.

In short, the present article will use the ideas of Dirac, of Battey-Pratt and Racey, and of Kauffman to argue that describing \hbar with observable crossing switches of unobservable strands – the so-called *fundamental principle* – explains and visualizes *all* quantum effects. Quantum mechanics, with its experimental observations, its axioms, its mathematical details, and its measurement process, will be derived from the topological and geometric aspects of crossing switches. In addition, it will be argued that crossing switches of unobservable strands are the *only* possible explanation, description, and visualization of the quantum of action \hbar that agrees with observations. Finally, it will be shown that the main difference between strands and the conventional continuum description of quantum mechanics explains its open issue: the origin of particle masses.

3 Crossing switches: observability and promises

In nature, *all* measurements use quantum effects and electromagnetism. All measurement apparatuses, all measurement units, and all measurement processes do so. In the strand model, Figure 11 illustrates the reason:

Statement 20: Crossing switches are observable because they couple to photons.

The detailed reason for modeling photons as rotating loops in a single strand will be given in Section 16. The coupling of crossing switches to photons occurs by *steric* effects due to strands pushing each other. Thus, the Dirac trick is observable because it generates observable crossing switches. Identifying a crossing switch with \hbar , as Dirac [9, 10], Battey-Pratt and Racey [12] did

Crossing switches *couple* to photons

Figure 11: Crossing switches *couple* to loops and thus to photons due to strands pushing each other. The structure of photons is explained in Section 16. The steric coupling of crossing switches and photons implies that crossing switches are *observable* physical processes and make measurements possible, despite the unobservability of strands. Measurements count crossing switches. As argued later on, the coupling implies the principle of least action. The coupling is also the Planck scale description of the *electromagnetic Feynman vertex* and thus of a *quantum jump*. The coupling geometry determines the fine-structure constant and produces atomic orbitals.

implicitly, and as Kauffman [14, 15] did explicitly, implies that crossing switches are observable. Crossing switches have an objective reality *even though* the strands are invisible.

Identifying Planck's quantum of action \hbar with a crossing switch implies that \hbar is *constant* and *invariant*, with the same value for all observers throughout the universe. Experiments [28, 29] confirm the conclusions, despite the theoretical possibility of the contrary [30].

Identifying a crossing switch with Planck's quantum of action \hbar further implies

Thesis 21: Not only are all quantum effects due to crossing switches; all measurements and all observations count crossing switches. They do so by counting photons.

The present article will confirm this statement in the domain of quantum mechanics. In this domain, the proposal to describe the quantum of action \hbar by observable crossing switches of unobservable strands requires checking eleven points:

1. The proposal must explain and visualize *indistinguishable* but *countable* elementary *fermions* with spin $\hbar/2$.
2. The proposal must explain and visualize the *smallest observable action* and the *quantization of angular momentum*.
3. The proposal must explain and visualize *wave-particle duality*, *de Broglie's relation*, *wave functions*, *Hilbert spaces*, *Schrödinger's equation* and *Feynman's path integral formulation*.
4. The proposal must explain and visualize *quantum jumps* induced by photons.
5. The proposal must explain and visualize the *non-commutativity of quantum observables*, as well as *unitary* and *self-adjointed* operators.
6. The proposal must explain and visualize Heisenberg's *indeterminacy relation*.
7. The proposal must explain and visualize *entanglement* between different particles.
8. The proposal must explain and visualize *light* and *photons* with their properties.
9. The proposal must explain and visualize *quantum measurements*, *Born's rule* for the observed probabilities, and the *lack* of hidden variables.

10. The proposal must explain and visualize *spinors*, *antiparticles*, and the derivation of *Dirac's equation* by Battey-Pratt and Racey.
11. The proposal must explain and visualize the *principle of least action*.

These eleven points reproduce the historical development of quantum mechanics after Planck discovered the quantum of action \hbar . In the following, all eleven points will be shown to be due to crossing switches of strands. Not all questions of quantum mechanics are treated. *Qubits* are only briefly mentioned. In their simplest realization, as nitrogen vacancies in diamond, qubits are lone localized fermions. Tangles and crossing switches model qubits [31]. *Tunneling*, not discussed in the following, arises due to the always existing, though low, probability of tangle diffusion across regions of high potential. Also other aspects of quantum mechanics remain to be explored.

To be convincing, crossing switches must explain *all* quantum effects, thus *all* relations that contain \hbar , also those *beyond* quantum mechanics. In particular, the ability to describe all measurements and observations with crossing switches implies

Thesis 22: Identifying \hbar with observable crossing switches of unobservable strands promises to *describe all of nature*.

In particular, it will be shown below that crossing switches *explain* why elementary particle masses are small fractions of the Planck mass and how they can be estimated *ab initio*. To complete the argument, derivations from other publications will be summarized, which have shown that crossing switches also *derive* the origin of quantum *field* theory, the interactions and the spectrum of elementary particles, the Lagrangian of the standard model with massive neutrinos, the nature of flat and curved vacuum, and the field equations of general relativity. In particular, strands explain the coupling constants and mixing angles [32, 33]. The precise calculation of the fine-structure constant from Figure 11 will be the topic of a subsequent article.

In short, crossing switches of unobservable strands are observable because they couple to photons. Crossing switches promise to explain and to visualize how \hbar plays a role in *all* quantum aspects of nature. In the following, *quantum mechanics* will be *deduced* from the fundamental principle of Figure 6, which forms the *only assumption* of the strand tangle model. All results and all consequences deduced from the fundamental principle are testable and falsifiable. To help visualize the results that follow, the dictionary in Table I lists the main correspondences between quantum mechanics and the strand tangle model that will be deduced in the following.

Table I: The correspondence between quantum theory and the strand tangle model.

Quantum Theory	Strand Tangle Model
Quantum of action \hbar	Change value due to a crossing switch of unobservable strands.
(Physical) action	Number of crossing switches.
Event	Observable crossing switch of unobservable strands, twist-induced.
Vacuum	Untangled, unobservable, fluctuating strands.
Principle of least action	Principle of fewest crossing switches.
Angular momentum	Number of crossing switches per rotation.
Physical observable	Specific arrangement and count of crossing switches.
Particle & type	Rational 3d tangle of strands of specific topology.
Spinning particle	Continuously rotating tangle core.
Antiparticle	Mirror rational 3d tangle rotating in the opposite direction.
Particle number	Number of tangle cores.
Elementary fermion	Non-trivial, i.e, localizable rational 3d tangle of 2 or 3 strands.
Spin $\hbar/2$	Due to the tethered rotation of an elementary fermion tangle.
Particle propagation	Combination of chiral core rotation, Dirac's trick, and strand hopping.
Quantum particle state	Average position, orientation, size, shape, and motion of a tangle core.
Wave function	Oriented crossing density of fluctuating strands in a tangle.
Superposition	Partial tangles connected by an untangled addition region.
Interference	Recombination of partial tangles, i.e., shrinking of stretched cores.
Probability density	Crossing switch density of fluctuating strands in a particle tangle.
Measurement	Decoherence due to buffeting by bath strands.
Indeterminacy relation	Due to strand shape fluctuations.
Operator	Tangle deformation.
Non-commutativity	Consequence of crossing switches.
Linear momentum	Number of crossing switches per length.
Energy	Number of crossing switches per time.
Particle mass	Core rotations per time, with corresponding crossing switches.
Gauge interaction	Reidemeister move in one tangle transferred to another.
Gauge boson	Topologically trivial rational 3d tangle due to a Reidemeister move.
Photon	Propagating and rotating loop on a strand.
Helicity & polarization	Core rotation sense & orientation.
Electric charge	1/3 of the number of signed topological chiral crossings.
Speed of light c	Minimum length, i.e., strand diameter, per minimum time.
P parity	Behavior after tangle mirroring.
C parity	Behavior after tangle mirroring and time inversion.
Virtual particle	Short-lived tangle of vacuum strands due to shape fluctuations.
Reactions & decays	Tangle rearrangements & splittings.
(Quantum) gravity	Exchange of gravitons, i.e., of twisted strand pairs.
Spatial curvature	Vacuum strands crossing at two macroscopically distant points.
Horizons & entropy	Tight, one-sided weaves of strands & their fluctuations.

4 Crossing switches, strands, double cover, and unitarity

We now point out the relationship between the crossing switch, Dirac's trick, the rotations of three-dimensional space, and unitary evolution. The general relationship between the crossing switches and rotations is illustrated in Figure 12. The relationship can be made precise mathematically.

Let $R(\mathbf{v}, \vartheta)$ denote a rotation by angle ϑ around an axis described by the vector $\mathbf{v} \neq \mathbf{0}$. It is a fact of geometry that the composition of two such rotations is another rotation of the same form. That is, for all points P , if $R(\mathbf{v}, \vartheta) \circ R(\mathbf{u}, \varphi)P = R(\mathbf{v}, \vartheta)(R(\mathbf{u}, \varphi)P)$ denotes the result of first rotating P about \mathbf{u} by φ and then rotating the result about \mathbf{v} by ϑ , the result can also be obtained directly by using another axis \mathbf{v}' by ϑ' , so that

$$R(\mathbf{v}', \vartheta')P = (R(\mathbf{v}, \vartheta) \circ R(\mathbf{u}, \varphi))P . \quad (1)$$

The rules for this composition of rotations can be expressed using the quaternions. Let $g = e^{\mathbf{v}\vartheta/2}$ and $h = e^{\mathbf{u}\varphi/2}$, where we take each axis to be described by vectors \mathbf{v} and \mathbf{u} of *unit* length in three-dimensional space. This means, for example, that $\mathbf{v} = v_i i + v_j j + v_k k$ where the components are real numbers satisfying $v_i^2 + v_j^2 + v_k^2 = 1$. Then, in quaternion multiplication, one has $v^2 = -1$ and $u^2 = -1$ so that $h = e^{\mathbf{u}\varphi/2} = \cos(\varphi/2) + \mathbf{u} \sin(\varphi/2)$ is a four-space quaternion. The rotation of $P = p_i i + p_j j + p_k k$ is then accomplished by the formula

$$R(\mathbf{v}, \vartheta) P = g P \bar{g} = e^{\mathbf{v}\vartheta/2} P e^{-\mathbf{v}\vartheta/2} . \quad (2)$$

This requires verification that we omit here. Note that g and $-g$ induce the *same* rotation since $(-g)P(-\bar{g}) = (-1)gP(-1)\bar{g} = (-1)^2 gP\bar{g} = gP\bar{g}$. This means that the unit length quaternions, which we denote by S^3 , map *doubly* to the rotations of three-space, which we denote by $SO(3)$.

The *double cover* $\Pi : S^3 \rightarrow SO(3)$ is most important for understanding the crossing switch, as we shall see. Also, to find the new axis and new angle for the composite rotation gh , one can multiply the corresponding quaternions:

$$gh = e^{\mathbf{v}\vartheta/2} e^{-\mathbf{u}\varphi/2} = (\cos(\vartheta/2) + \mathbf{v} \sin(\vartheta/2))(\cos(\varphi/2) + \mathbf{u} \sin(\varphi/2)) \quad (3)$$

and rewrite the result as

$$gh = \cos(\vartheta'/2) + \mathbf{v}' \sin(\vartheta'/2) . \quad (4)$$

We omit the details (which are easy). In this way, the quaternions unlock the mystery of rotations in three-space.

Now we return to the map $\Pi : S^3 \rightarrow SO(3)$ so that we can see the shape of $SO(3)$ as a three-dimensional topological space, and see how it is covered twice by S^3 . To do this, consider first a ball B^3 of radius π , as illustrated in Figure 13. For each diameter of the ball, we consider angles ϑ marking that diameter, thus with $[-\pi \leq \vartheta \leq \pi]$. Thus the rotations $R(\mathbf{v}, \vartheta)$ in $SO(3)$ are in correspondence with the points in the ball, except that, along a diameter, the point at π must be identified with the point at $-\pi$. In other words, we have $SO(3) \cong B^3 / \sim$, where *antipodal points* on the boundary of the ball B^3 are *identified*. This space B^3 / \sim is usually called \mathbb{RP}^3 , the three-dimensional *projective space*.

Another way to understand $\mathbb{RP}^3 = B^3 / \sim$ is to take two copies of B^3 joined along their S^2

The **crossing switch** is related to a **rotation by 2π** and to the **Dirac trick**

Figure 12: The relations between a crossing switch, a rotation by 2π , and Dirac's trick are illustrated. In particular, it is shown how *two* crossing switches are equivalent to *no* crossing switch.

Figure 13: The three-dimensional ball B^3 defines a rotation for each point on a diameter, and thus for each point in the ball. Each diameter is also a *loop* of rotations that arises due to the identification of the two endpoints.

boundaries to form the three-sphere S^3 . We can describe the three-sphere as $S^3 = \{(x, y, z, w) \in \mathbb{R}^4 \mid x^2 + y^2 + z^2 + w^2 = 1\}$. Now let us take a point $(x, y, z, w) \in S^3$. Then its antipodal point on S^3 is $(-x, -y, -z, -w)$. Then we can set $\mathbb{RP}^3 = S^3 / [(x, y, z, w) \sim (-x, -y, -z, -w)]$. We have the map $\Pi : S^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{RP}^3$ that is two to one. This is a topological picture of our mapping

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi : S^3 &\rightarrow SO(3) \\ g &\rightarrow g P \bar{g} \ , \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where S^3 is the set of the unit quaternions in four-space.

Now the point is that the mapping $S^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{RP}^3$ allows us to understand the nature of Dirac's trick by relating it to the fundamental group $\pi_1(\mathbb{RP}^3)$. In Figure 13, the loop α in B^3 / \sim starting from a $-\pi$ rotation and ending with a $+\pi$ rotation is a *loop of rotations*. This loop is the generator of $\pi_1(\mathbb{RP}^3) \simeq \mathbb{Z}_2$. In other words, the twist by 2π in Figure 12, or equivalently, the path from a rotation by π to one by $-\pi$ in the ball of rotations in Figure 13, represents the generator of the fundamental group of $SO(3) = \mathbb{RP}^3$. The double loop α^2 in the ball of rotations is homotopically trivial: it is homotopic to the identity, i.e., it can be contracted to a point. This corresponds to the unwinding of the tethered 4π rotation in Dirac's trick. See reference [15] for more about this.

From the point of view of $\Pi : S^3 \rightarrow SO(3)$, when a fermion turns by 2π , it lifts to a path from 1 to -1 in the unit quaternions S^3 . Another 2π turn lifts it back to 1. The entire 4π loop of rotations can thus be deformed away. Quantum evolution corresponds to the actions of the quaternions in $S^3 = SU(2)$. Thus we see how the strand topology is in harmony with quantum evolution. Strands lift rotations to $SU(2)$, thus to a unitary transformation. The crossing switch in

Figure 12 can be seen as the *lift* or *jump* between sheets in the covering space $S^3 = SU(2)$ of the rotations in 3-space $SO(3) = \mathbb{RP}^3$. This yields

Statement 23: Dirac's trick gives a topological interpretation of the double covering of $SO(3)$ by $SU(2) = S^3$.

Statement 24: Hence one can directly model unitary evolution in terms of strand motions in three-space.

Statement 25: Strands imply the importance of complex numbers in quantum theory.

In short, strands imply that quantum evolution and quantum processes are topologic-geometric. In the strand model, the fundamental process associated with the quantum of action \hbar is the crossing switch that occurs in Dirac's trick. Strands relate topology, the geometry of rotations, the double covering of real $SO(3)$ by unitary $SU(2)$, crossing switches, and the unitarity of quantum processes. Just as, in $SO(3)$, the homotopy of loops of rotations is not known directly, the details of the strand movements are not observable macroscopically, i.e., from the outside of the strand world. Only the end result, corresponding to *jumping* from one sheet of the covering space to another due to a crossing switch, is available to the (quantum) observer. In this way, unitary evolution comes into correspondence with what can be observed, and the hidden topology of the strand world is the origin of the observable phase and magnitude of the wave function, as will become clear shortly.

5 Deducing particles, spin, and statistics from crossing switches

The fundamental principle, with the ideas of Dirac, Battey-Pratt, and Racey, implies the following

Main definition: A *moving spinning elementary particle* is an observable *rational 3d tangle* consisting of 1, 2, or 3 unobservable open fluctuating strands forming a moving rotating tangled *core* that is *tethered*, i.e., anchored, to the cosmological horizon. Moving fermions continuously perform Dirac's trick. This is the *strand tangle model* of particles.

Definition 27: A *rational 3d tangle* is an unknotted generalized braid whose tethers are distributed in three dimensions.

Examples of rational 3d tangles and counterexamples are given in Figure 14. Particles are thus *tangled*, but *unknotted* configurations of strands, with unobservable tethers spanning 3d space. Strand tangles fluctuate in shape. To reproduce spin, all particles are *dynamic* topological structures. Figure 15 shows a spinning electron tangle. A general illustration of spinning motion, valid for all leptons, is Figure 16. Whenever a lepton or any other fermion moves through space, its core continuously performs Dirac's trick and thus induces observable effects. In simple terms, the main definition due to the fundamental principle implies

Statement 28: Non-vanishing *spin* is the intrinsic rotation of tangle cores.

In particular, a continuously rotating non-trivial rational tangle performing a continuous sequence of Dirac tricks describes a *spinning* fermion, like the example of Figure 16. For any *elementary* fermion, the fundamental principle, Dirac's trick, and the fermion trick fix the value of the *spin*, i.e., the intrinsic angular momentum with

Statement 29: Non-trivial tangles of two or three strands leaving in different directions

Rational 3d tangles – or 3d braids: vacuum and quantum particles

Knotted tangles and links: *not occurring in nature*

Figure 14: The simplest topological structures made of strands are illustrated. Particles are rotating *rational 3d tangles*, which are formed by braiding tethers of open strands in three dimensions *without* knotting them. For particles at rest, the tethers – i.e., the anchored connections to the cosmological horizon – are distributed equally in 3d space. Section 16 shows that the *continuously rotating* topologically trivial tangle of one strand with a loop has all the properties of the photon. It was shown elsewhere [31–36] that the simplest rotating *trivial* tangles of two or three strands have all the properties of the other elementary gauge bosons and of the graviton, that the Higgs boson also arises, that the simplest *non-trivial* rotating tangles of two strands have all the properties of quarks, and that the simplest *non-trivial* rotating tangles of three strands have all the properties of leptons. The tangle *core* of all fermions is chiral, as is observed. Tangles of four or more strands represent *composite* systems. *Knotted tangles*, whether open or prime, *cannot* and *do not* arise in nature. Also mathematical *knots* and *links*, which contain closed strands, *cannot* and *do not* arise in nature.

describe elementary spin $\hbar/2$ fermions.

The spin value $\hbar/2$ also implies that a spin flip of such a particle realizes the smallest measurable action \hbar , as observed. In other words, the fundamental principle of strands proves

Statement 30: The spin-statistics theorem holds for all elementary fermions.

Indeed, the spin-statistics theorem is observed to be valid throughout nature [38]. Once tangle cores are identified with particles, the main definition, together with the fermion trick, proves

Statement 31: *Different particle types* are described with tangles of *different topology*.

Statement 32: *Identical particles* are described with tangles of *identical topology*.

Figure 15: The figures show the rotating tangle of three strands that represents a spinning electron. The rotating chiral triangle at the center, the tangle *core*, determines the position of the electron, its charge, its chirality, and its lepton generation. The tether fluctuations are not shown; only their *average* motion is shown. The region of curved strands, including and around the tangle core, yields the wave function. The animation, accessible at desmos.com/3d/46kkmamfwy, was produced by Desmos user Ronwnor.

Statement 33: *Identical particles* are indistinguishable.

Statement 34: *Counting* particles occurs by counting tangle cores.

Statement 35: The *exchange* of particles is due to *orbital* rotation of tangle cores.

Statement 36: Non-trivial rational 3d tangles behave as *fermions*, i.e., as *matter particles*.

Statement 37: *Pauli's exclusion principle* holds for identical fermions.

The indistinguishability of identical matter particles and their fermion properties solve the Gibbs paradox and yield the Sackur-Tetrode equation for monoatomic gases. Pauli's exclusion principle explains the shell structure of every atom. It has been tested to high precision [39].

References [31–36] explored and derived the *classification* of simple rational 3d tangles. The

Figure 16: The animation by Jason Hise, available at motionmountain.net/videos.html#strands or at reference [37], visualizes Dirac’s trick for all spinning leptons with their six tethers. The spinning central cube symbolizes the core of the lepton tangle. The cube rotates *twice* before returning to the starting configuration. The factor of 2, due to Dirac’s trick, visualizes spin $\hbar/2$. The tether fluctuations are not shown; only their average motion is shown.

classification reproduces the spectrum of the elementary particles with their spin, parities, charges, and generations. In particular, rational 3d tangles consisting of *three* strands with non-trivial topology behave as *leptons*, the family of matter particles containing the electron, the muon, the tau, and their neutrinos. Figure 14 also provides a glimpse into the tangles of (unbroken) gauge bosons. Their trivial tangle topology reproduces their integer spin and their boson exchange behavior, thus completing the spin-statistics theorem. All properties deduced from the boson tangles are as observed [31–36]. Photons, the most common gauge bosons, are explored in detail in Section 16.

Rational 3d strand tangles and their fluctuations also imply

Definition 38: A *virtual particle* is a short-lived tangle that appears and disappears through fluctuations that locally tangle the untangled vacuum strands.

It turns out that *only* rational 3d tangles describe and explain pair creation, annihilation, decay, particle reactions, and particle mixing. These processes are part of quantum field theory and are explored elsewhere [31–36].

In short, this section showed that the fundamental principle identifying crossing switches with \hbar leads to modeling spinning matter particles as rotating rational 3d tangles of unobservable strands. This model reproduces the main aspects of matter particles, namely their spin $\hbar/2$ and their fermion behavior under exchange. Strand tangles thus imply the spin-statistics theorem for fermions, describe their countability, and explain the indistinguishability of identical matter particles in all their observed aspects. Any contrasting observation, such as the discovery of an elementary particle with spin $3\hbar/2$, would immediately invalidate the strand tangle model.

6 Deducing the limit for action and the quantization of angular momentum

In the fundamental principle, although strands are unobservable, crossing switches of strands represent the simplest observable processes in nature. The definition of crossing switches implies that *incomplete* crossing switches are *unobservable*. Strands thus yield

Statement 39: Measured action is never smaller than \hbar , which provides its measurement unit.

The statement agrees with all observations [3], from photon counting to magnetic resonance imaging. Strands thus describe Planck's discovery that \hbar is a *quantum* of action. Every physical action thus consists of action quanta.

In nature, physical action measures change. As mentioned in Section 2, the quantum of action \hbar is the quantum of change. In the strand model, crossing switches are *countable*. This yields

Statement 40: Every *change* in nature is composed of crossing switches.

Statement 41: Every *process* in nature is composed of crossing switches.

Statement 42: *Action* counts the number of crossing switches.

The following sections will confirm this description in detail.

In rotating systems, *angular momentum* is defined as *action per full rotation*. Because partial crossing switches are not observable, this implies

Statement 43: *Orbital angular momentum* is quantized in integer multiples of \hbar .

The tethered rotation illustrated in Figure 3 and Figure 7 and its double cover of $SO(3)$ proves

Statement 44: *Spin* is quantized in integer multiples of $\hbar/2$.

The conclusions agree with all observations about elementary particles and composed systems, including nuclei and atoms [40].

In short, this section showed that because crossing switches can be counted, strands imply a lower action limit given by \hbar and imply that *total* angular momentum is quantized in multiples of $\hbar/2$. Any contrasting observation, such as the discovery of an anyon in three dimensions, would immediately invalidate the strand tangle model.

7 Defining wave functions as oriented crossing densities

In nature and in all experiments, the position of quantum matter particles is observed to be fuzzy. Particle positions must be described by probability densities. Experimentally, every moving fermion is described by a fuzzy phase that rotates perpendicularly to a fuzzy path. Experimentally,

Figure 17: The Schrödinger wave function and the probability density emerge from an electron tangle via the crossing fluctuations and the resulting oriented crossing density.

every fermion must be described by a complex wave function whose squared modulus yields a probability density.

In the strand tangle model, a moving quantum particle is described by a fluctuating tangle whose tangle core rotates. The reason is provided by

Statement 45: Tangles, crossings, and wave functions all have magnitudes and phases.

For a fermion, Figure 17 and Figure 18 illustrate the general relation between tangles and wave functions. Specifically, the figures show

Statement 46: The *wave function* or *quantum state* Ψ is the *oriented crossing density* among the strands of a fermion tangle – thus *ignoring* vacuum strands. Its unit is the number of crossings per square root of volume.

Statement 47: A rotating fermion tangle is the rotating *skeleton* of its wave function.

Statement 48: The *probability density* is the *crossing switch density* of a fermion tangle. The probability density is defined as the number of crossing switches per volume occurring in a minimum time ($\sqrt{4G\hbar/c^5}$, twice the Planck time).

These statements generalize the ideas of Battey-Pratt and Racey [12] and provide the foundation of quantum mechanics, as will be shown in the following. The *type* of particle is defined by the tangle *topology*. In contrast, the *quantum state* of the particle is determined by the average tangle *geometry* and the average tangle *dynamics*.

Figure 18 illustrates how the oriented crossing density of a particle tangle yields the wave function, including a local amplitude and a local phase. The equivalence arises because a crossing at a point has the *same geometric properties* as a wave function at a point: a crossing has an *amplitude* – determined by the locally shortest strand distance – and a *phase* – determined by the orientation of the shortest distance with respect to a chosen reference direction. It must be underlined again that only crossings among the strands of the particle tangle define the wave function. Figure 19 implies amplitude and phase, in particular

Statement 49: The (local) *amplitude* R of a wave function is determined by the (local) average crossing density.

The strand tangle model for wave functions

Figure 18: In the strand tangle model, a spinor *wave function*, often modeled with a flag, is the average *oriented crossing density* of a fluctuating fermion tangle. The *average* is taken over the shape fluctuations occurring during a few Planck times. The graph on the upper right illustrates how the geometric parameters of a tangle crossing – the region of locally shortest strand distance – leads to a density and phase. The main figure illustrates the conceptual steps leading from fluctuating strands to fluctuating crossings, to the wave function with a central total phase (the flag direction), and to a probability density. The figure is somewhat simplified: in reality, the phase of such a localized wave function depends on the position.

Statement 50: This (local) *phase* φ of a wave function is half the average *crossing phase* α , thus $\varphi = \alpha/2$. The (local) *phase* of a wave function thus describes the (local) average orientation of the tangle core with respect to a chosen reference direction.

Statement 51: *Averages* for R and φ are taken during a few Planck times over *all* strand fluctuations of the tangle, without any speed limit.

Fluctuations in particle tangles are *induced* by all the surrounding strand segments that form empty

Strand crossings have the same properties as **wave functions**: **amplitude** and **phases**.

Figure 19: A strand crossing consists of two skew strand segments separated by the (locally) shortest distance s . Due to the impenetrability of strands, the shortest distance s is never shorter than the diameter of the strands, the minimum length in nature – which can be neglected in most experiments. A strand crossing defines an amplitude, a main phase α , and several further phases; it thus defines the *same geometric properties* as a wave function at a point. The drawings show that the (main) *phase* α describes the direction in which the shortest distance vector *points*. The dotted direction defining *zero phase* is a matter of choice. Regardless of this choice, phase differences are always defined uniquely. The drawings also define the *crossing axis* as the sum of the two suitably chosen tangent vectors at the two endpoints of s . The angles or phases β , γ , and δ play a role in spinors, as told later in the text.

space. In nature, fluctuations occur in all strands, those of particle tangles and those of the vacuum. Every wave function $\Psi(x, t)$ depends on position and time. This does not contradict the short-time averaging of fluctuations, because macroscopic physical time t is never defined, in practice, with a precision better than about a thousand Planck times, whereas the averaging time is only a few Planck times.

In total, the above statements yield

Statement 52: The Schrödinger wave function Ψ – the simplest of all wave functions because it neglects spin and relativity – is a *complex-valued* function given by

$$\Psi(x, t) = R(x, t) e^{i\varphi(x, t)} = \frac{1}{N^{1/2}} R'(x, t) e^{i\alpha(x, t)/2} . \quad (6)$$

In this relation, the *magnitude* $R(x, t)$ specifies the local *crossing density* of the particle tangle and the *phase* $\varphi(x, t) = \alpha(x, t)/2$ specifies the average local orientation of the crossings with respect to a reference direction. The natural number N is the minimal number of crossings in the particle tangle and is used to normalize the wave function. In the example of the figure, the minimal crossing number is $N = 3$. The wave function is thus *complex* because it describes an *oriented crossing density* – at each point in space.

Additional examples of how wave functions and fluctuating tangles of strands correspond are regularly given and explored in the following. In particular, plane waves are illustrated in Figure 25, and hydrogen orbitals are illustrated in Figure 28.

Tangles of strands imply that each wave function describes a *single* quantum system. Tangles thus conform to the Pusey–Barrett–Rudolph theorem making the same statement [41] and to the views of Hobson [42]. Tangles thus also agree with all experiments showing that wave functions can be measured, such as references [43, 44]. In simple words, strands confirm that each atom is a spherical object.

Also the probability density follows from strands. The spatial regions with high probability density are the regions where the tangle core, with its crossings and crossing switches, is found most frequently. Because a crossing switch requires a crossing before and a crossing after the switch, the crossing switch density is related to the *square* of the crossing density. Because a crossing switch requires that the crossings before and after the switch differ by a rotation by π , thus by a multiplication by i , the probability density, i.e., the *crossing switch density*, is the *squared modulus* of the crossing density.

In short, this section showed that defining the particle wave function $\Psi(x, t)$ as the *oriented crossing density* of the fluctuating particle tangle *qualitatively* reproduces magnitude, phase, and probability density. Tangles and their crossings thus explain why wave functions are *complex-valued*. Any contradicting observation would immediately invalidate the strand tangle model. Next, strands will be shown to deduce the *quantitative* aspects of wave functions.

8 Deducing superpositions of quantum states, interference, and Hilbert spaces

In nature, all experiments, including interference and diffraction, consistently show that quantum states can *superpose*. Specifically, quantum mechanics is *linear*: quantum states described by wave functions can be added and multiplied. All such linear combinations, with complex coefficients, of solutions of the Schrödinger equation are again solutions of the equation. Such superpositions, for example of particles located at two different positions, are often in contrast with everyday experience. Superpositions describe that quantum states can contain a multiplicity of possibilities for the different measurement results that can arise in experiments. Superpositions of states, together with the Hilbert space they generate, are a central feature of quantum mechanics.

We shall now proceed to describe visualizable versions of superpositions using strands and to explore their properties. The start is the summary of the previous sections, which provided

Statement 53: The *quantum state* or *wave function* of a fermion, denoted by Ψ , is determined by a specific (average) position, orientation, size, shape, motion, and rotation speed of the (fluctuating) rational 3d tangle *core* describing the particle and its oriented crossing density, while its (fluctuating) *tethers* leave in directions of 3d space that are as different as possible.

Linear combination of tangle states

Figure 20: A superposition or linear combination of two states representing a fermion localized at *two different positions* is visualized. A position measurement *dissolves* the untangled *addition region*, free of crossing switches and shown in grey, either to the left or to the right.

Specifying the wave function as the oriented crossing density of a fermion tangle almost automatically implies a visualization of superpositions. The superposition of a fermion at two *different positions* in space is illustrated in Figure 20. The superposition of a *spin-up* and a *spin-down* state is visualized in Figure 21. The basis for the superpositions of states with *different phases* is illustrated in Figure 22. The superposition arising in the double slit experiment for an electron is shown in Figure 23. Superpositions and interference for photons are visualized in Section 16. The figures imply

Definition 54: A *superposition*, or normalized linear combination, of two basis states consists of two rotated, *partial* tangles separated and connected by an untangled *addition region*, free of crossings and crossing switches. Equivalently, a superposition is described by a tangle whose shape and evolution *interpolates* between the basis states with the help of an untangled addition region. Again equivalently, superpositions are *stretched* tangles.

To show the equivalence of this definition and the conventional one requires

Definition 55: A *partial tangle* is a tangle for which a part of its core is ‘pulled’ away. Partial tangles *cannot* be detected; only complete tangles can be detected, after collapse, as told in Section 17.

Definition 56: An *addition region* is a topologically untangled region of strands connecting

Figure 21: A superposition of a spin-up and a spin-down state is visualized. It also visualizes such a state for a qubit. Spin-up and spin-down states differ in the rotation direction of the core. The untangled addition region, free of crossing switches and shown in grey, is the volume between two concentric spheres and enables the outside and the inside to rotate in opposite directions. For a fascinating animated version of such a superposition, produced by Jason Hise, see [youtube.com/shorts/-KGW3QvwFuE](https://www.youtube.com/shorts/-KGW3QvwFuE). A spin measurement dissolves the untangled addition region either towards the outside or towards the inside.

partial tangles.

Statement 57: In the *scalar multiplication* of a state by a complex number $re^{i\theta}$, the phase θ *rotates* the tangle core, whereas the magnitude $r < 1$ *reduces* the effective core extension to a partial tangle. In total, such a scalar multiplication yields a *rotated partial tangle*.

Superpositions are therefore only possible between states with the same topology, thus between states describing the same particle type and the same particle number. The states being added

Figure 22: The basis for the strand explanation of interference is illustrated: in a region of space, two merging crossings connected by strands that dissolve their untangled addition region can superpose constructively (top) or destructively (bottom).

determine the shape of the untangled addition region. Superpositions of more than two states can also be visualized with strands. In this case, there are several addition regions. We note that in the above definition, superpositions are only defined for normalized states and always yield normalized states. The tangle definition of strands thus takes normalization into account right from the start.

A complete definition of the concept of superposition has to define how the precise *geometric shape* of the addition region is determined when two partial tangles are given. The precise specification for the time-behavior of *partial tangles* is also needed. Finally, the precise *time-dependency*

Figure 23: Tangles explain electron interference. In a double-slit experiment, depending on the phase difference between the two paths, the electron tangle interferes constructively or destructively with itself. The upper left image shows the wave description. In the upper right image, the wide arrows show the most probable paths in Feynman's path integral description. The lower left image shows the strand model. The hopping of the core from strand to strand allows ignoring the strands of the material with the slits. The hopping allows partial electrons to pass through both slits. The lower right image shows the strand description of Feynman's path integral formulation. The strand model visualizes both the description in terms of wave functions and that in terms of path integrals.

of the addition region needs to be specified, including the average geometric details of the *untangled strands* in it, recalling that, in general, the two partial tangles rotate. Though the figures given in this section provide a first visual impression, a precise, mathematically satisfying definition of superposition still has to be worked out. This section is thus a visual guide and a motivation for a precise mathematical theory of tangle superpositions that is still in development.

The visualization of superpositions is more vivid with the following

Statement 58: A measurement of a superposition *dissolves* the untangled addition region by *shrinking* it towards one or the other eigenstate and thus randomly yields one of the two options.

The shrinking and dissolution is realized by the *buffeting bath strands* that are part of every measurement apparatus. The measurement process will be explored and visualized with strands in

Section 17.

The strand definition of a superposition allows the study of its properties. Even though many possible shapes can realize an addition region, its properties can be formalized. Adding states using an untangled addition region is intrinsically *commutative*. The addition of states is also *associative* and has a *neutral element*, defined by untangled (vacuum) strands. The addition of (partial) rational 3d tangles also defines a *negative element*, given by the mirror (partial) tangle. Finally, the addition and the change of the relative weights in partial tangles are *distributive*, as is easily checked. Thus, addition regions model the *linearity* of wave functions and yield

Statement 59: Strand tangle superpositions form a *linear space* or *vector space*.

In nature, linear superpositions of states lead to *interference*. Figure 22 illustrates the strand basis of constructive and destructive interference, and Figure 23 illustrates an electron in a double-slit experiment. Depending on the relative phase of all states arriving *in a given region of space*, their superposition can increase or decrease the local crossing density, thus the local crossing switch density, and therefore the detection probability in that region.

To produce interference, the electron tangle core approaching the two slits in Figure 23 must be *spread out* in the transversal direction and cover both slits. To visualize the double-slit experiment completely, one needs to keep in mind that tangles can also propagate by exchanging strands:

Definition 60: Rational 3d tangles describing particles can propagate by *hopping* from a strand to the *next*, by shedding one strand and incorporating a new, *neighboring* strand.

Statement 61: To preserve tangle topology, *independent* hopping of *partial* tangles is *excluded*. Only *complete* tangles can hop from a strand to a neighboring one.

In free space, tangles moving with and without hopping are indistinguishable. In addition, we have

Statement 62: The unobservability of strands and of their fluctuations *excludes* the description of hopping with an equation of motion for strands.

This result [31], though disappointing, is necessary to maintain the agreement with quantum mechanics and the exclusion of non-contextual hidden variables. Only oriented crossing densities can have an equation of motion, as shown shortly.

The double-slit experiment illustrated in Figure 23, an electron state spread out in space can pass the two slits *only* if its partial tangles hop onto three *common* strands on the other side of the slits. If this is not the case, the electron is absorbed on the screen. As soon as one slit is closed, the figure implies that two-slit interference *changes* to one-slit interference. The strand tangle model thus reproduces the impossibility of distinguishing the paths taken and the slits passed by an electron in the two-slit experiment. All this is observed. Strands thus confirm that an electron tangle always passes *both* slits.

The illustrations of the double-slit experiment in Figure 23 also visualize that unobservable strands with observable crossing switches reproduce both the wave function description and the path integral description of fermions. This is one of the charming aspects of strands. This topic will be explored further in the next section.

Behind the two slits, the two partial tangles reunite and superpose. The result of the superposition depends on the *relative phase* of the two partial tangles. In particular, in the case of opposite phases, the superposition of the partial tangles yields a region of untangled vacuum strands and thus of destructive interference. The final tangle *detection* on a scintillation screen behind the

double slit is explored and visualized in Section 17. In total, this yields

Statement 63: Strands reproduce quantum superpositions and interference.

So far, this conclusion agrees with all experiments, including the most extreme ones [45]. In the future, it would be worthwhile to investigate delayed choice experiments and quantum eraser experiments with strands.

The mathematical description of tangle states can be expanded. It is possible to define an *inner product* between two tangle states with the help of the crossing *switch* density that arises when changing from the conjugate of the first state to the second [31].

Definition 64: The *conjugate* tangle is a tangle in which the sign of all crossings is changed. (It is also shifted in time by a minimum time, twice the Planck time.)

Definition 65: For fermion states, the *inner product* is the number of crossings appearing (per minimum time) when changing from the conjugate of the first state to the second state.

The inner product of a state with itself determines the crossing switch density, i.e., the probability density. Simply stated, in the fundamental principle of Figure 6, the left configuration corresponds to Ψ , and the right one to Ψ^* . With the definition of the inner product, it is possible to determine when tangles are orthogonal.

Definition 66: Two tangles are *orthogonal* if *no* crossing switch arises when deforming the conjugate of the first tangle into the second tangle.

The next section will use this definition for plane waves. Exploring the properties of the inner product for superpositions of states is straightforward. By construction, the inner product is sesquilinear, its norm is positive definite, and the state space is complete [31]. This yields

Statement 67: Wave functions fulfill all the axioms of a Hilbert space.

In particular, by construction, moving tangles *conserve* the integral of the probability density, as is observed. The conservation property already implies most of quantum mechanics [46, 47].

Because each particle tangle generates *its own* Hilbert space, we get

Statement 68: A particle tangle is a quantum field.

Because tangles are countable, and because tangles and anti-tangles can arise from the untangled strands of the vacuum, tangles of the same topology define a *Fock space*. No “second quantization” and no “superselection rules” are necessary in the strand tangle model. Quantum field theory is not treated in this article; it is explored elsewhere [31–33, 36]. It can be noted that once interactions are introduced as observable tangle deformations, particle tangles allow the visualization and the deduction of the Gårding-Wightman axioms, of the Osterwalder-Schrader axioms, and even of the Haag-Kastler axioms of quantum field theory.

It should be remarked that the concepts of superposition, of Hilbert space, and of Fock space arise *exactly*, as do the various axioms of quantum field theory, only in the case that strands are assumed to have a *vanishing* radius and thus allow exact locality and exact point particles. This assumption is in agreement with all experiments in quantum theory. However, it will be shown in Section 23 and Section 24 that to achieve agreement with *all* observations, thus including observations *beyond* quantum theory, the vanishing radius has to be changed to the *unmeasurably small* radius given by the Planck radius. The difference only affects Planck scales and is unnoticeable in quantum theory.

Moving rotating tangles are propagating particles

Figure 24: Top: A *slowly* moving particle tangle has a tangle core with a central phase rotating and precessing around the direction of motion. Bottom: For *rapidly* moving particle tangle, both movements are tighter and faster.

In short, this section confirmed that the definition of \hbar with crossing switches implies that wave functions are *oriented crossing densities* of fluctuating tangles. Conversely, for each wave function, there is an underlying fluctuating tangle *skeleton*. Superpositions are described by partial tangles connected by an untangled *addition region*. Partial tangles and untangled addition regions explain and visualize *interference* in complete agreement with observations and combine the description with wave functions and that with Feynman's path integral. Strand tangles naturally yield Hilbert spaces and imply the conservation of probability, in agreement with all observations so far. The next sections will complete this description and will reproduce all quantitative and mathematical aspects of quantum mechanics.

9 Deducing matter waves from strands

In nature, every moving quantum particle is observed *also* to behave like a *wave*, and thus to be *extended*. Experiments confirm the statement by de Broglie [49]: the *wave number* $k = p/\hbar$ is given by the particle momentum p divided by the quantum of action \hbar . Experiments also confirm that the *circular frequency* ω of the wave is determined by the energy E via the relation $\omega = E/\hbar$, as first conjectured by Planck [50].

A snapshot of an (almost) plane electron wave travelling to the right with its probability density and phase

Figure 25: Top: The phase of a moving wave packet depends on the position, as seen in the illustration by Bernd Thaller from his website [48] (used with permission). The illustration visualizes the phase of the wave function with color and the amplitude with saturation. Bottom: The strand model for an almost plane wave consisting of one electron is illustrated. The core is stretched, wound up, and rotates continuously. Right side: The tangle of an electron at rest has the same topology but a simpler shape.

In the strand model, the wave function is the oriented crossing density and thus is extended. For a moving particle, the tangle orientation changes along its path. In simple terms, when a particle moves, its chiral tangle core continuously rotates, as illustrated in Figure 24, Figure 25, and Figure 26. For fermions, this implies

Statement 69: Particle motion is a continuous sequence of Dirac tricks.

This supersedes the older idea that point particles move through points of space. The phase rotation of a moving particle is due to the rotation of the chiral tangle core. Each full rotation of the core yields an observable crossing switch. As explained above, every observation records a change in nature, and change is measured with action. Because action is defined as the number of action quanta, and because momentum is defined as action per length, this yields

Statement 70: A particle's *momentum* counts the crossing switches *per length*.

Each crossing switch is characterized by \hbar . Therefore, the momentum of an advancing rotating tangle is given by $p = 2\pi\hbar/\lambda = \hbar k$. In other words, de Broglie's expression for particle wavelength λ follows from crossing switches of strands. Likewise, energy being action per time yields

Statement 71: A particle's *energy* counts the crossing switches *per time*.

Figure 26: In the strand tangle model, an advancing particle core with given energy-momentum continuously rotates. In the case of a fermion, this implies a continuously occurring Dirac trick. The arrow describing the core phase – neglecting spin and its precession – traces out a *helix*. Each turn leads to a crossing switch. The *wavelength* of the helix specifies the *momentum* because momentum is action per length, thus the number of crossing switches per length. The rotational *frequency* of the helix specifies the *energy* because *energy* is action per time, thus the number of crossing switches per time. Note that for an *exact* plane wave, the transverse size of the core, measured in the plane orthogonal to the motion, fluctuates *without bounds* and *without speed limit*; such fluctuations transport no energy.

Thus, the energy of an advancing rotating tangle is $E = 2\pi\hbar f = \hbar\omega$. Planck's expression for the frequency f and the angular frequency ω of a particle *follows* from crossing switches of strands. Crossing switches of strands also yield the particle properties of light, as explained in Section 16.

In short, the fundamental principle identifying \hbar with a crossing switch implies modeling a moving fermion as a moving rotating chiral tangle core, analogous to a tethered pinwheel or a tethered maple seed moving through the air and continuously performing Dirac's trick. This model for moving particles explains why \hbar appears in de Broglie's expression for the wavelength and in Planck's expression for the frequency. It might well be that strands provide the first explanation for the two expressions. Any contrasting observation would immediately invalidate the strand tangle model. In other words, the fundamental principle deduces *matter waves* and *wave-particle duality*. The visualization of particle motion with rotating strand tangles continuously performing Dirac tricks allows the deduction of the free Schrödinger equation in two ways.

10 Deducing path integrals and the Schrödinger equation from tangles

Experiments confirm that the *phase* of every quantum particle rotates around the direction of motion like an arrow rotating in a helix around the path, as told by Feynman [51] and as illustrated in Figure 26. In particular, experiments confirm that non-relativistic particles with negligible spin follow Schrödinger's equation [52–56].

The rotation of the tangle core of a moving particle implies Feynman's description of a particle as a moving, rotating arrow. Feynman's description then can be used to define and calculate the

The strand tangle model for a *fermion* in the *path-integral* formulation

Figure 27: In the strand tangle model, the wave function can also be seen as the consequence of Feynman's *path integral* description. Contracting the tangle core to a point and recalling that tethers are unobservable, an advancing particle is reduced to a rotating arrow or flag attached to a moving point particle. The different possible paths of the moving arrow then yield the wave function.

wave function. The two steps are illustrated in Figure 27. In the first step, both the tangle core and the region taken up during the Dirac trick are contracted to a *negligibly small*, point-like volume. Recalling the unobservability of tethers, a *moving* and *rotating* particle tangle core thus becomes a moving point with an attached rotating arrow. The moving point yields a particle *path*. In the second step, as told by Feynman [51], the various possible paths of the moving and rotating point particle are integrated and their final phases are added. This yields the wave function.

The rotation of a particle tangle advancing through the vacuum resembles the rotation of a *pinwheel* or of a *maple seed* [57] moving through the air. These everyday processes differ from quantum particle motion in three aspects: a quantum particle is tethered, a quantum particle experiences no friction, and the particle's wavelength and rotation frequency depend on its speed. Nevertheless, maple seeds, pinwheels, and quantum particles share an important aspect:

Statement 72: A quantum particle moving through a vacuum *rotates* because the *chiral* shape of its tangle core is put into rotation by *vacuum strands* encountered during its motion.

Recalling that the vacuum itself consists of fluctuating, untangled strands helps in visualizing why the chirality or handedness of a particle tangle core moving through the vacuum leads to core rotation. Figure 24 illustrates that the tangle of a moving particle gets wound up while advancing.

The wound-up tails can be taken to visualize an (almost) plane wave function advancing through space. Now and then, fluctuations rearrange the wound-up strands with the help of Dirac's trick. As explored in Section 23, the probability per time of these rearrangements and the amount of core chirality determine the mass value of a particle.

Moving tangles of strands also visualize the connection between *action* and *phase* highlighted by quantum theory. When advancing along a given path, every particle tangle rotates. Each full rotation of the moving tangle increases the phase by 2π and the action by producing a crossing switch. Thus, action and phase are related in the strand model, as they are in quantum theory.

The strand tangle model implies that a wave function can either be described as a fluctuating *loose* tangle, or as a fluctuating *contracted* tangle. This equivalence is the reason for the equivalence of the Schrödinger picture and of Feynman's path integral formulation [51]. Both approaches allow deducing the Schrödinger equation. We start with Feynman's approach and thus with

Statement 73: The many possible paths taken by a quantum particle result from the many possible motions of its contracted tangle core and its fluctuating strands.

The amount of phase rotation, or core rotation, that the particle accumulates on each possible path depends on the length of the chosen path and on the momentum of the particle. The effects on the core of all possible paths leading to a given final point are combined.

In nature and in the strand tangle model, when a point-like particle propagates from an initial point to a final point, the final phase is determined by the path length, the wavenumber k , the angular frequency $\hbar k^2/2m$, and the mass m . In nature and in the strand tangle model, at the final point, the phases for all the possible paths *superpose* following the rules of Section 8 on superpositions. As a consequence [58], the Feynman propagator for a free, point-like, rotating, and non-relativistic particle moving from an initial point x to a final point x' in a time Δt , described by the unitary time evolution operator U , arises by integrating over all wave numbers k :

$$\langle x|\hat{U}(t, t + \Delta t)|x'\rangle = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{ik(x-x')} e^{-\frac{i\hbar k^2 \Delta t}{2m}} dk . \quad (7)$$

This specific case is the *Schrödinger propagator* describing the evolution of a free non-relativistic quantum system, ignoring spin. *This propagator is equivalent to the Schrödinger equation* [58]. The close relation between the propagator and the Lagrangian can be seen by rewriting the exponentials using

$$e^{i\theta} = e^{\frac{i}{\hbar}(p\Delta x - E\Delta t)} = e^{\frac{i}{\hbar}(p(\Delta x/\Delta t)\Delta t - E\Delta t)} = e^{\frac{i}{\hbar}(mv^2 - E)\Delta t} = e^{\frac{i}{\hbar}(mv^2/2 - V)\Delta t} = e^{\frac{i}{\hbar}L\Delta t} , \quad (8)$$

where θ is the accumulated phase and L the Lagrangian, as expected.

Using the propagator, the evolution of a wave function and its corresponding tangle can be described as a sum over all possible paths of a point particle with a rotating arrow. The many possible paths are due to the many possible strand fluctuations. The description of electron interference as a sum over paths is illustrated in Figure 23. All aspects of the path integral description are recovered from the strand tangle model. For example, the result that the propagator is nonzero outside the light cone results from the lack of a speed limit for strand fluctuations. The description of photon interference is illustrated later, in Section 16.

In short, because contracted tangles with unobservable tethers advance like rotating arrows,

fluctuating particle tangles contracted to a point with a phase arrow reproduce Feynman's path integral formalism. Because the motion of rotating arrows implies the Schrödinger propagator, fluctuating tangles of strands imply the Schrödinger equation. Again, wave functions are confirmed to be oriented crossing densities. Identifying \hbar with a crossing switch confirms that a moving fermion can be seen as a fluctuating, point-like, rotating chiral tangle core of unobservable strands, resembling a tethered pinwheel or a tethered maple seed moving in the air.

11 Re-deducing the Schrödinger equation from tangles

A second deduction of the free Schrödinger equation was used by Schrödinger himself. In nature, when a free fermion moves, its *wave function evolves*: the phase *rotates* and the probability distribution *diffuses*. The rotation frequency, i.e., the fermion energy, and its diffusion are observed to be related to the wavelength, i.e., to the momentum.

In the strand tangle model, the evolution is due to fluctuations in the fermion tangle, which in turn are induced by the fluctuations of the surrounding vacuum strands. As already mentioned, in a moving, rotating tangle, the *phase* describes the orientation of the tangle core. In the non-relativistic case, the (average) *shape* of the tangle core is *fixed*; the core rotates *rigidly*. The phase, i.e., the orientation of the core, rotates in a plane orthogonal to the direction of motion and traces a helix around the direction of motion, as pictured in Figure 26. The helix arises by idealizing Figure 24. Any phase rotation is a rotation in a plane. A rotation by $\pi/2$ in the complex plane perpendicular to the axis of the helix is a multiplication by i . Phase rotation is thus the reason that the wave function, the oriented crossing density, is complex-valued [51].

A rotating phase helix, due to repeated Dirac tricks of a tangle, has two important properties. Because each Dirac trick or crossing switch yields \hbar , because crossing switches occur at crossings because the frequency is the number of Dirac tricks or crossing switches per time, one can rewrite the energy-frequency relation $E = \hbar\omega$ deduced in Section 9 with

Statement 74: The energy E of a tangle with crossing density Ψ is given by $E = i\hbar \partial_t \Psi$.

The faster the rotation, the higher the energy. Indeed, Planck's experiments, like all other observations, confirm the relation between energy and frequency.

Correspondingly, the tighter the helix, the more crossing switches per length arise. Momentum is defined as the number of action quanta per length. Again, each crossing switch yields \hbar , and crossing switches occur at crossings. Again, one can rewrite de Broglie's momentum-wavenumber relation $= \hbar k$ deduced in Section 9 using the crossing density, i.e., the wave function. The fundamental principle implies that in a rotating helical series of crossings, the displacement of the whole helix leads to crossing switches. Taking into account the correct sign yields

Statement 75: The momentum p of a tangle with crossing density Ψ is $p = -i\hbar \partial_x \Psi$.

The tighter the helix, the higher the momentum.

The relation between the temporal and the spatial aspect of core rotation is described by the mass m . The mass value describes the tightness of the helix for a given momentum and a given rotation frequency. As Schrödinger showed and strands confirm, inserting the expressions for energy and momentum into the non-relativistic dispersion relation $E = p^2/2m$ for a free particle

of mass m yields

$$i\partial_t\Psi = -\frac{\hbar}{2m}\partial_{xx}\Psi . \quad (9)$$

This is the well-known *free Schrödinger equation*. It describes how the oriented crossing density – the wave function Ψ – evolves over time and space. In particular, the equation relates the phase rotation on the left-hand side to the diffusion, i.e., to the broadening of the wave function on the right-hand side. This evolution is observed for all non-relativistic situations in which spin and potentials can be neglected.

Mathematically, two tangle helices representing plane waves of two different wavelengths have a special property. When deforming (the conjugate of) a helix with a given wavelength into a helix with a shorter wavelength (as an example), there are, as a whole, no crossing switches. This surprising result is a consequence of Dirac’s trick: even though a shorter wavelength in Figure 26 suggests more crossings, the Dirac tricks compensate them. The resulting lack of crossing switches confirms that tangles of different wavelengths are *orthogonal*. The result also confirms that the Hilbert space of a free particle is infinite-dimensional, as expected. As a consequence, tangles can be used to reproduce Fourier decompositions for arbitrary wave functions of free particles. The resulting proof of the completeness of the Hilbert space of a free particle – for strands with vanishing radius – is left to the reader. As a consequence, free particle wave functions can be described with tangles.

In short, this section showed: using the fundamental principle to define wave functions as oriented crossing densities of fermion tangles leads to phase rotation, to wave function diffusion, and allows *deducing the free Schrödinger equation* for the case of non-relativistic motion with negligible spin effects. For this case, any observed deviation would immediately invalidate the strand tangle model. The origin of fermion mass values is explored in Section 23.

12 Visualizing atomic orbitals and quantum jumps with strands

In conventional quantum theory and in the strand tangle model, one can distinguish the time-dependent and the time-independent Schrödinger equation. Solving the time-independent Schrödinger equation implies finding the corresponding average crossing density, by averaging over the rotation of the tangle core. An important system is the hydrogen atom. The wave functions of the various hydrogen energy states are standing electron waves around the proton that are constructed from the free electron de Broglie waves [58]. Figure 28 gives two examples of hydrogen orbitals due to the time-independent Schrödinger equation and two snapshots of the underlying fluctuating strand tangles. The strands of the proton do not change the image and have been ignored. Ignoring the proton strands is possible due to the fermion trick described in Section 2.

In nature and in the strand tangle model, an electric field is a flow of virtual photons and leads to a *potential* [32]. The strand model of photons is introduced in section Section 16. The potential quantifies the effects of photons on tangle crossings illustrated in Figure 11. All interactions, also the electromagnetic one, *deform* tangle cores [34, 35, 59]. The deformation leads to a difference between E and p^2/m . The potential V describing the electric field quantifies the dispersion relation for energy-momentum, which is $E = p^2/2m + V$ in the case that spin and relativistic effects are neglected. The potential V thus describes how virtual photons change the relation between

Two examples of hydrogen orbitals

Figure 28: Two hydrogen orbitals and snapshots of the corresponding electron strand tangles are illustrated. The wave functions are oriented crossing densities due to strand shape fluctuations. The virtual photons realizing the attraction between the electron and the nucleus are not drawn.

electron energy and momentum. In conventional quantum theory, the potential *deforms* the wave function of a free particle to a wave function of a particle in a potential. In the same way, in the strand tangle model, the potential shapes the average electron tangle core that describes a free electron into a deformed average tangle core for the electron in the potential. In both cases, the amount and direction of the reshaping depend on the strength and direction of the potential.

The chiral crossings of the electron tangle represent the *electric charge* [32]. The potential surrounding the proton distributes the chiral crossings of an electron in the way illustrated in Figure 28. The potential results from virtual photons. Strands imply minimal coupling, charge conservation, and Maxwell's equations, as told elsewhere [32]. Given that the Schrödinger equation does not take into account spin, relativistic effects, and antiparticles, the 1s state of Figure 28 is completely characterized by an average distance of the three electron crossings from the proton. The proton potential and the kinetic energy of the electron determine the average distance from the proton. The symmetric tangle shape for the 1s state visualizes the vanishing orbital velocity of the electron. Planck's quantum of action \hbar determines the average width of the distance fluctuations, as in usual quantum mechanics. The 1s state is a standing wave resulting from a *deformed* free particle state, as expected. In the 2p state, the electron tangle core is extended, and its fluctuations are modified by the angular momentum – the orbital speed – of the electron tangle, yielding the well-known dumbbell shape. Also the 2p state is a standing wave produced by the potential of the proton, and is a deformed free particle state. As always in the strand tangle model, there is no mathematical difference between the crossing densities of the average strand shapes and the wave functions that are solutions of the Schrödinger equation.

If the electron tangles are simplified by cutting off the tethers near the core, the motion of the

resulting oriented structures yields the atomic spin state visualizations of Heusler and Ubben [60]. This establishes a direct connection between the tangle model and such visualizations.

In 1913, in his model of the atom, Bohr introduced the concept of a *quantum jump*. He used the term to describe the sudden change of state when a photon is emitted or absorbed by an electron around a nucleus. Above, Figure 11 had illustrated the general process of how a state interacts with a photon. The orbitals in Figure 28 show two states in a hydrogen atom between which a quantum jump can take place. Strands imply that quantum jumps are sudden, intrinsically quantum, and effectively local. In other words,

Statement 76: Quantum jumps are due to crossing switches.

There are several ways to express the result. Quantum jumps are due to the double covering of $SO(3)$ by $SU(2)$. Quantum jumps are due to the switch of sheet in the covering. Quantum jumps are due to the insertion of 2π twists. This yields

Statement 77: Quantum jumps are the visible shadows of a non-trivial covering space.

In total, we can thus say:

Statement 78: Quantum theory is a natural consequence of topology.

Again, we stress that describing the *exact* mathematical *shapes* of a tangle in an atom or in any other quantum system, or even describing their shape evolution, is *impossible*. Such a description would provide hidden non-contextual variables, and thus would contradict all observations that prove that no such variables exist. Only *average* shapes play a role in quantum theory and in nature. Any description of exact shapes is also *untestable* because the strands themselves are unobservable. Despite the yearning to know and describe nature in more detail than with wave functions, strands do not fulfill this yearning. The impossibility of observing or thinking about exact strand shapes is explored further in Section 17. The only possible statements about strand shapes in a quantum system are *statistical*: only oriented crossing *densities* of strands can be determined. In other words, only the evolution of wave functions can be described. The figures in this article assume that snapshots of strands can be taken. It must be clearly stated that this assumption is *unphysical*; however, the figures help *visualizing* strands and their relationship to wave functions. *The strand visualization of wave functions thus remains open to questioning.*

As a note, strands also reproduce the *Aharonov-Bohm effect*, which is due to the effect of the magnetic potential in a region without a magnetic field. This occurs because the magnetic potential, like the electric potential, can be modeled with virtual photons and affects the phase of the tangle and thus of the wave function. Equivalently, the extension of particle tangles describes the non-local aspects of the effect.

In short, also in the presence of potentials, wave functions are oriented crossing densities of fluctuating tangles, tangles are fluctuating skeletons of wave functions, and tangles imply and visualize the Schrödinger equation. In particular, tangles and their oriented crossing densities visualize atomic orbitals, and crossing switches induced by photons describe *quantum jumps*. While not completely discontinuous, crossing switches retain the essence of Bohr's idea of quantum jump. Any contrasting observation would immediately invalidate the strand tangle model.

13 Deducing operators and Heisenberg's canonical commutation relation

In all *discrete* dynamical systems that are characterized by smallest time and length intervals, operators of physical observables do not commute, as shown by Kauffman [61–65]. In all such systems, the amount of discreteness determines the amount of *non-commutativity*.

Also nature is discrete and non-commutative: action is characterized by the smallest measurable value \hbar . As expected and observed, in nature and in quantum mechanics, this smallest action value determines the non-commutativity of operators describing physical observables. However, time and length are observed to be *continuous*. Strands and their crossing switches explain this apparent contradiction. Because operators act on tangles, they imply

Statement 79: Operators are smooth *deformations* (isotopies) of strand tangles.

In general, tangle deformations do not commute, as was shown above with the core rotations that behave like the non-commuting unit quaternions. The strand model is inherently non-commutative. Two classes of operators are central to quantum mechanics.

Unitary operators deform *only the tethers* of particle tangles; they have complex eigenvalues of magnitude 1. Such operators keep the shape and the topology of the tangle *core untouched*. For example, the *time evolution operator* rotates the tangle core around the path of the particle, without changing the core's size, shape, or topology. The time evolution operator rotates the core without deforming it, thus keeping it *rigid*, coils up the tethers, and leads to Dirac tricks. Strands thus visualize that the time evolution of particle tangles is unitary.

In contrast, *Hermitian* or *self-adjointed* operators describe physical observables and have real eigenvalues. A Hermitian operator acting on an eigenstate multiplies it by the eigenvalue. In the strand tangle model, a Hermitian operator acting on a quantum state keeps the topology unchanged but changes the shape of *both* the tethers and the core. The specific shape change depends on the operator. For example, when acting on a *general* state or tangle, the *position operator* \hat{x} multiplies a particle tangle by the continuous position coordinate x and *increasingly scales* the state along the coordinate x . The eigenstates of the position operator are tangles that are *localized*, or shrunk, at a specific position: the eigenstates are δ -functions. This result highlights that the usual definition of Hermitian operators effectively *hides* the fluctuations and processes occurring at the strand level. The strand radius and the Planck scale are assumed to be unmeasurably small.

The derivation of de Broglie's relations for particle tangles in Section 9 showed that the *momentum operator* is given by $\hat{p}_x = -i\hbar \partial_x$. The eigenstates of the momentum operator \hat{p}_x can be visualized as tangles whose cores are helically coiled around the x -axis, as visualized in Figure 24 and Figure 26. Apart from scaling, such an eigenstate does not change when the momentum operator \hat{p}_x acts on it. In contrast, when acting on a *general* state or tangle, the momentum operator \hat{p}_x *rotates* the state around the x -axis and *increases* the state amplitude where the helix is tight.

Combining the effects of the position operator \hat{x} and the momentum operator \hat{p}_x yields an important consequence for their *commutator*, i.e., for the quantity defined as $[\hat{x}, \hat{p}_x] = \hat{x}\hat{p}_x - \hat{p}_x\hat{x}$.

Statement 80: The relation $\hat{p}_x = -i\hbar \partial_x$, implies that the commutator between momentum and position satisfies

$$[\hat{x}, \hat{p}_x] = i\hbar . \quad (10)$$

This is *Heisenberg's canonical commutation relation*. In simple words, Hermitian operators do

not commute in general. The canonical commutation relation arises once \hbar is identified with a crossing switch and de Broglie's relations are deduced from this identification. Historically, the canonical commutation relation was the basis of the first formulation of quantum theory, developed and formulated by Heisenberg in 1925. Strands clarify the origin of the canonical commutation relation directly from crossing switches: tangle deformations do not commute.

The canonical commutation relation (10) is also valid for the y and z directions. The strand tangle model further shows that the commutators between the \hat{x} and \hat{y} operators, or between \hat{x} and \hat{p}_y , which concern independent tangle deformations, all vanish. This reproduces textbook quantum mechanics and all observations.

A completely different train of thought leads to *almost* the same canonical commutation relation. Combining the smallest observable action $W \geq \hbar$, the highest measurable speed $v \geq c$, and the highest measurable mass per length ratio $m/l \geq c^2/4G$ or the equivalent maximum measurable force $F \geq c^4/4G$ [66], yields $l \geq \sqrt{4G\hbar}/c^3$. Thus, there is a *minimum length* in nature, given by twice the Planck length. Likewise, a *minimum time* occurs in nature, given by $\sqrt{4G\hbar}/c^5$, twice the Planck time. A crossing switch takes at least one minimum time [31]. As told in the [Appendix](#), the minimum length *implies* the existence of *discrete*, extended, fluctuating, and common constituents of space and particles: strands [67]. The minimum length is also the smallest possible length measurement *error* in nature [67–79]. Likewise, the minimum time is also the minimum time measurement *error*. These minimum errors *prevent* the observation of discrete points, of discrete position changes, of discrete time shifts, and of single strands. Nature and the strand model thus contain spatial and temporal discreteness, – which have been extensively explored, e.g., by Ord [80] – but also prevent their observation.

In every *discrete* dynamical system, the fundamental time and position steps lead to a non-vanishing commutator of position and momentum. Time steps lead to a difference between the effects of the momentum operator followed by those of the position operator and the effects for the opposite order of operators, as shown by Kauffman [61–65]. These publications show that an almost canonical commutation relation appears whenever the time shift and the length shift operators are discrete, i.e., whenever there are smallest measurable time and length intervals. In that case, the temporal distance between two measurements is always at least one minimum time Δt . Each momentum measurement requires a speed measurement. Each speed measurement requires two position measurements and a time measurement. Two position measurements x and x' differ at least by the smallest length interval Δx . A time measurement yields at least a minimum time. Therefore, measuring position first and then momentum differs from measuring momentum first and then position. Indeed, the commutator $[\hat{x}, \hat{p}_x]$ yields

$$[\hat{x}, \hat{p}_x] = \hat{x}\hat{p} - \hat{p}\hat{x} \geq x'm \frac{x' - x}{\Delta t} - m \frac{x' - x}{\Delta t} x = m \frac{(x' - x)^2}{\Delta t} \geq m \frac{(\Delta x)^2}{\Delta t} \quad (11)$$

and thus relates the commutator to the fundamental discreteness of the system. The value of the commutator quantifies the commutativity with a diffusion constant, as expected. Both nature and strands provide minimum measurable length and time values. As a consequence, the commutator $[\hat{x}, \hat{p}_x]$ is related to these minimum values. Inserting the minimum length, the minimum time, and the maximum elementary particle mass $\sqrt{\hbar c/4G}$ – half the Planck mass [67] – into the commuta-

tor (11) yields

$$[\hat{x}, \hat{p}_x] = \hbar . \quad (12)$$

In simple words, *assuming* Planck-scale discreteness implies that the commutator between momentum and position operators is quantified by \hbar . However, this calculation does not yield the imaginary unit i in the commutator, because i is related to the rotation encoded in the definition of crossing switches. Naively discrete, grid-like systems do *not contain* the three-dimensionality that is implied by crossing switches. Despite the understanding that naively discrete, grid-like systems bring to various aspects of nature, they *miss* all those aspects of nature that characterize three spatial dimensions, namely spin, fermions, quantum phase, wave functions, entanglement, topological structures, and the complete commutation relation. Strands do confirm the discreteness of nature, but also confirm that nature's discreteness is not based on a grid, but on fluctuating filiform constituents.

Nature thus makes a surprising, almost self-contradictory statement. Minimum length and time imply that space and time are “somehow discrete” and “somehow non-commutative”. However, at the same time, deviations from the continuity of space and time are *not measurable*: the minimum measurement errors *wash out* and *hide* the discreteness and non-commutativity of space and time. Due to the minimum measurement errors, strands are unobservable and space and time appear continuous. As a consequence, for every observer, nature is *partially discrete* and *partially continuous*. Both discreteness and continuity are approximate. This yields

Statement 81: The only observable discrete aspect and the only non-commutative aspect of nature is the discreteness of *action*, characterized by \hbar .

This limitation of observations leads to the canonical commutation relation and to the rest of quantum mechanics, while keeping space and time *effectively* continuous and commutative. Nature's partial, apparent, approximate, effective, and emergent *continuity* appears in space and fields. Nature's partial, apparent, approximate, effective, and emergent *discreteness* appears in particles and quantum effects. Strands describe both aspects.

In short, this section first showed that operators *deform* tangles. Because crossing switches encode a fundamental non-commutativity and a fundamental, fluctuating, washed-out, unobservable discreteness of nature, identifying Planck's quantum of action \hbar with a crossing switch implies the canonical commutation relation for position and momentum operators. Strands predict no observable deviations from the relation. Nevertheless, space and time *remain* continuous and commutative *for all practical purposes*. Any contrasting observation, for any observable, at any energy, would immediately invalidate the strand tangle model.

14 Deducing Heisenberg's indeterminacy relation from a crossing switch

In nature, the quantum of action \hbar appears in the indeterminacy relation, also called the uncertainty relation, that applies to many observables describing physical systems. The relation is a well-known aspect of wave-particle duality and has been confirmed in all observations.

In the strand model, the indeterminacy relation is a direct consequence of the wave properties of matter particles, of the Schrödinger equation, or of the commutation relation. In addition, the strand model also allows a direct, visual derivation.

In the strand model, the tangle describing a quantum system continuously fluctuates in shape. A general system configuration will resemble the middle configuration illustrated in the fundamental principle of Figure 6. Now, *partial* crossing switches are unobservable, as told in Section 6, and every observation requires at least one *complete* crossing switch, as told in Section 17. After a measurement, a system has a specific crossing configuration. Therefore, the measurement of a general two-strand configuration, like the central one in the crossing switch of Figure 6, will randomly yield one of two possible crossings, and thus randomly yield one or no crossing switch. The strand fluctuations in the quantum system and in its environment determine which crossing arises and whether one or no crossing switch is detected. Because the fundamental principle implies that any two crossing configurations are separated by at least \hbar , one gets

Statement 82: The measurement of physical action W is uncertain by an amount

$$\Delta W \geq \hbar/2 . \quad (13)$$

This *action indeterminacy relation* applies to all physical systems, thus to all matter and to all radiation. It agrees with all real and thought experiments [81–83]. The action indeterminacy relation follows because \hbar and all measurements on physical systems are defined with the help of crossing switches, because every measurement counts crossing switches, and because, due to fluctuations, the counting of crossing switches is always uncertain by *half* a crossing switch.

The indeterminacy in the number of crossing switches yields an indeterminacy for *complementary* quantities, i.e., for quantities whose product yields action, such as position and momentum:

$$\Delta x \Delta p \geq \hbar/2 . \quad (14)$$

This is Heisenberg’s original *indeterminacy relation* [3]. Strands imply the indeterminacy relation because momentum and position can both only be measured with the precision of half a crossing switch. In the same way, crossing switches also imply an indeterminacy relation for angular momentum and phase, as well as one for system energy and decay time. The strand model confirms

Statement 83: On the quantum scale, all physical measurements of continuous observables are inherently *undetermined*, thus *fuzzy*. The minimal fuzziness for complementary observables is given by $\hbar/2$.

All this is observed. The indeterminacy, or fuzziness, arises because all physical systems, even single quantum particles, consist of constituents that are both discrete and extended.

In short, this section deduced the appearance of $\hbar/2$ in Heisenberg’s indeterminacy relation from the rounding error when counting the crossing switches that define continuous observables. Strands predict the lack of observable deviations from the indeterminacy relation. Any contrasting observation would immediately invalidate the strand tangle model.

15 Deducing quantum entanglement

Quantum entanglement is a fascinating aspect of nature observed in the quantum domain. An *entangled* state is a multi-particle quantum state that is not separable, i.e., a state that cannot be described as a product of independent single-particle states. Every entangled state is a superposi-

Figure 29: Left: an *entangled* spin 0 state of two fermions is illustrated. The figure also illustrates two entangled qubits. The untangled addition region is the grey volume between two ellipsoids. The addition region around the two particles prevents either particle from being described as a separate or independent system. The size and shape of the addition region describe the relative weight of the two states forming the superposition. Right: after spin measurement, the addition region either has shrunk to zero or expanded to the cosmological horizon. As a result, one of two possible separable two-particle states is observed.

tion of two or more many-particle states. As a consequence, quantum entanglement implies that a measurement of a single particle from an entangled set immediately influences the measurements of the other particles. After such a single-particle measurement, an entangled state is observed to be immediately disentangled, either completely or partially. Entanglement is an active domain of research [84], mainly because of its importance in quantum computing. We explore a few aspects.

The textbook example of entanglement, proposed by Bohm [85], is given by two spinning particles in a spin 0 state that are carefully pulled apart. It was realized experimentally, a few decades later, for example by Fry [86]. In such experiments, when the spin of one particle is measured, the spin of the other is always found to have, immediately, the opposite sign, independently of their distance. This apparently superluminal effect can be observed in experiments with photons of opposite helicity departing from a special common source or with antiparallel electron spins kept at a fixed distance in quantum computers.

In the strand model, the description of entanglement is a direct consequence of the description of superpositions given in Section 8, once superpositions are generalized to multi-particle states.

As an example, the strand description of two-particle spin entanglement is illustrated in Figure 29. The strand description visualizes that an entangled state is not separable: because of the addition region, the two tangles are not independent. Any measurement dissolves the untangled addition region; in this case, the dissolution happens either outwards or inwards. Strands thus visualize how an entangled spin 0 state yields, after a measurement, one of two possible unentangled situations, in which both tangles are independent, but whose total spin remains 0. The description of entanglement with tethers in Figure 29 can be generalized by imagining that the two tangle cores *depart* from each other, while continuously being surrounded by an expanding addition region. The strand description of superpositions thus implies

Statement 84: Quantum *entanglement* results from *topologically entangled tethers*.

As soon as this visualization is completed with spin measurement devices that dissolve the entanglement region either inwards or outwards, strands reproduce the well-known demonstration of entanglement provided by Mermin [87]. In this way, the addition region and strand fluctuations explain the violation of Bell’s inequality.

Strands visualize entanglement as a consequence of the *topological* and the *geometric* behavior of tethers. The strand description of entanglement also visualizes that, during any measurement of spins separated by a macroscopic distance, the tethers and their crossings move faster than light. Nevertheless, no information or energy – i.e., no crossing *switch* – moves faster than light. Strands thus reproduce the *apparent* non-locality of entanglement.

The idea that quantum entanglement has a topological origin has been explored with limited success in the past [88–97]. In contrast, the description of entanglement using tethers has the advantage of arising naturally from the model for wave functions and of avoiding any ad hoc cutting and reconnecting processes. For example, suitably connecting the tethers at the cosmological horizon recovers the classification of multi-particle entanglement by Quinta and André [89].

Tangles reproduce superpositions and entanglement also for more involved situations. In particular, by generalizing Figure 29 to *three* particles, Greenberger–Horne–Zeilinger (GHZ) states [98, 99] can be modeled. The description of such GHZ states with tangles avoids the limitations of the attempts to describe them with Borromean rings [92]; rings and their cutting do *not* capture all aspects of three-particle entanglement and measurement. In particular, the description of entanglement with tethers visualizes that certain three-particle states lead, depending on the measurement, either to three unentangled one-particle states or to an unentangled one-particle state and an entangled two-particle state. This result cannot be modeled with Borromean rings.

It is worth highlighting an aspect of strand entanglement that is already noticeable when exploring fermion behavior and the Pauli principle: strands imply and confirm that *many-particle states* ‘live’ in *three spatial dimensions*. No additional dimensions are necessary to describe multi-particle states. The result arises because in each region of space, *each* nearby particle produces a non-zero value of its own crossing density and thus of its own wave function.

This brief overview of entanglement did not cover many topics. For example, exploring *quantitative measures for entanglement* using tethers or analyzing the tether description of *quantum teleportation* are topics for future exploration.

In short, this section showed that identifying \hbar with a crossing switch reproduces the quantum entanglement of fermions via the topological entanglement of particle tangles in three dimensions. Strands imply that entanglement has all the observed properties predicted by quantum mechan-

A **photon** is described by a moving and rotating arrow \uparrow

The twist, or first Reidemeister move, yields a **$U(1)$ Lie group**, because keeping the encircled strand segment fixed after a double twist, the tethers can be rearranged to the original situation.

The above rearrangement yields a second, *equivalent* **model for the photon** and its motion:

Photon motion results in $m = 0, S = 1, P = -1, C = -1$. For most observers this yields a rotating and moving crossing switch. A photon can also move by hopping from one strand to the next.

Figure 30: The structure and the motion of photons are illustrated. Strands are unobservable, but crossing switches are observable. The strand model of a circularly polarized photon is possible because strands *do not provide* resistance to deformation or to torsion, unlike everyday ropes. Photons propagate over macroscopic distances by loops *hopping* from one vacuum strand to the next. During photon propagation, the chiral loop continuously rotates.

ics. Any contrasting observation, such as any observation faster than light, would immediately invalidate the strand tangle model.

16 Deducing the properties of light and photons

In 1899, Planck discovered that light consists of countable light quanta or *photons* [2]. The existence of photons explains blackbody radiation, the photoelectric effect, the buildup of interference patterns, and the observations of entanglement. Photons are massless, neutral, and have negative parity, two possible helicity values, spin \hbar , energy $\hbar\omega$, and wavelength $2\pi\hbar c/E$. The speed of photons, the speed of light c , has three essential properties. It is *invariant*, it is the *maximum* speed for physical systems, and it is *unattainable* for systems with mass.

Figure 30 shows the strand tangle model for a moving photon. A *circularly polarized* photon is described by a moving, continuously rotating strand segment, i.e., by a continuously occurring first Reidemeister move, or twist [32, 36], on a single strand. The core of a photon tangle is a loop. The rotation axis points along its direction of motion. The two possible rotation directions of the segment yield the two possible photon helicity values. After one full rotation, fluctuations return the tethers to their previous configuration. This yields spin \hbar . It is useful to recall that strands *do not* possess or allow torsion. The direction of motion is *independent* of the asymptotic tether orientation. During its motion, a photon core will generally *hop* from one strand to an

Linearly polarized photon encountering a polarizer

Figure 31: Strands explain how a *polarizer* affects a linearly polarized photon. The figure illustrates the situation for a linearly polarized photon core moving from the reader, almost along the line of sight, towards a polarizer oriented at an angle to the photon polarization. During the motion, the *hopping* of the photon core from strand to strand is implied. Polarizers yield a specific polarization at the expense of light intensity.

adjacent strand. The simple hopping of loops from one strand to a neighboring one implies that photons are *bosons*. The size – thus, indirectly, the curvature – of the photon core describes the wavelength of the photon. As a curiosity, strands thus imply that radio-frequency photons can have cores much larger than a kilometer, the wavelength of low-frequency radio waves. In the strand tangle model, photons are thus far from point-like structures. Only their crossings are (almost) point-like. *Linearly polarized* photons, discussed by Dirac in his text [100], are represented by a twist rotating along an axis *perpendicular* to their direction of motion. The freedom of choosing the angle between the rotating loop and the phase visualizes and explains U(1) gauge invariance. The strand model of photons enables defining electric and magnetic fields, deducing Maxwell's equations, and reproducing quantum electrodynamics, as told elsewhere [32, 36].

In the strand model, a photon, like all other elementary particles with spin, advances through the vacuum strands like a maple seed or a pinwheel moves through the air. In nature, the chirality of the seed wings relates motion and rotation. In the strand model, the chiral shape of the photon core relates motion and rotation and yields its negative P and C parities. The fluctuations of space are predicted to have no effect on photon propagation. (In fact, the fluctuations are the origin of the propagation.) Because no effect disturbs the propagation of a photon, its lifetime is larger than any measurable value. The motion through space usually occurs by *hopping* of the photon core from one strand to an *adjacent* one. As expected from a topologically trivial tangle, photons have no mass and no electric charge. The motion of photons *defines* the speed of light. Because the observer defines the vacuum strands of its reference frame, and because photons always hop from one vacuum strand to the adjacent one, the speed of light is always given by one minimum length per minimum time, i.e., always given by the value c . Therefore, the speed of light is *invariant* and

Figure 32: Strand tangles explain *photon interference* in the double slit experiment as a consequence of the superposition of *partial* photons. Depending on the relative phase between paths, a photon passing a double slit leads to constructive or destructive interference. Top: the traditional wave and particle descriptions. Bottom: the corresponding strand descriptions. The wide arrows show the paths of the particles – or, equivalently, of the partial photons. Also in this set-up, during propagation, a rotating photon tangle core *hops* from one strand to the next. Strands confirm Dirac’s statement that a photon can only interfere with itself.

independent of the motion of the observer. In particular, there is no way to change the effective speed of light by running after a light beam or towards it, or by moving the light source, or by hitting a light pulse with an advancing or receding mirror. All this is observed.

In nature, the speed of light is *unattainable* for massive particles. In the strand tangle model, matter particles also contain chiral cores, and thus they also move through a vacuum like a maple seed or a pinwheel, as shown in Figure 14 and Figure 16. In contrast to photons, fermions can only advance through a vacuum with the help of Dirac’s trick. The trick occurs with low probability and thus slows down fermions. Therefore, strands imply that fermions *cannot attain* the speed of massless photons, which do not need the Dirac trick to advance. It is an interesting exercise to map the geometric parameters of a crossing, illustrated in Figure 19, to the physical parameters of a photon. Section 18 will do so for fermions.

In nature, when a linearly polarized photon hits a *polarizer* at an angle, due to the interactions

Figure 33: The figure illustrates the distinction between two *partial photons*, with a segment rotating at a general angle to the direction of motion, and two *complete photons*, where the angle vanishes.

with the electron wave functions in the polarizer, two processes can occur: either the photon is absorbed, or it is transmitted. If it is transmitted, it acquires a new polarization direction. Figure 31 shows that strands yield the same result. Strands also confirm that the transmission probability depends on the relative angle between the polarizer and the photon polarization. The probability is 100% if the polarization direction of the photon and of the polarizer coincide. The larger the relative angle, the lower the transmission, until it reaches 0% for perpendicular orientations. The strand model description of linearly polarized photons thus visualizes the observations produced by polarizers.

In nature, photons are usually observed in detectors that absorb them, such as eyes or digital cameras. These detectors convert photon absorption into an electric signal. In the strand tangle model, photon detection is described as a transfer of the energy of the rotating photon to an electron tangle. This energy transfer yields the electric signal generated by the detector.

In nature, photons *interfere*. The strand description of the photon double-slit experiment is illustrated in Figure 32. A photon can pass the two slits if the curved partial photon segments *hop* through the two slits in such a way that, on the other side, they land on the *same* strand. Depending on the relative phase of the two partial photons, the interference behind the two slits yields constructive or destructive regions. The strand description visualizes Dirac's well-known statement that a photon only interferes with itself [100]. Strands also visualize how the wave

Figure 34: The observed interference produced by a Mach-Zehnder interferometer is illustrated. The strand description is also given, showing the rotating partial photon tangles and their addition region.

description and the particle description arise. No difference to the usual description of interference arises. The addition regions can also be thought to visualize the recently proposed *dark states* of light [101]. The subtle geometric and topological differences between two partial photons and two complete photons are illustrated in Figure 33.

In nature, the observations with a Mach-Zehnder interferometer contradict the idea that, at a beam splitter, a photon is either reflected or transmitted. Instead, all observations confirm that a photon takes both paths. Because the interference at the last beam splitter is constructive, every photon is detected in only one of the two detectors, in contrast to naive expectations. Figure 34 illustrates the explanation provided by the strand tangle model. The first beam splitter produces a pair of partial photons that reunite at the last beam splitter. The wavelength of the photon is encoded in the curved strand segments, i.e., in the partial photons. The strand description explains all observations by visualizing that the photon follows both paths. In the case of interference, particle tangles are spread out over macroscopic distances. And in each such case, a photon only interferes with itself.

Careful experiments by Clauser, Aspect, Zeilinger and their collaborators showed that two photons of opposite polarization can be in an *entangled* state with a vanishing total spin. When the polarization of one photon in such an entangled pair is measured, the polarization of the other photon is automatically and immediately fixed to the opposite sign and the entanglement is destroyed. Figure 35 illustrates the situation of two such entangled photons before and after the polarization measurement. As in the case of fermions, strands reproduce the quantum entanglement of photons

Figure 35: Top: an *entangled* state of two photons with total spin 0 and opposite velocities. Bottom: the two possible situations after the polarization of one of the photons has been measured. Section 17 explains how strand *buffeting* during measurement yields one of the two possible situations.

with topological entanglement.

In short, this section showed that strands imply

Statement 85: The photon tangle, a trivial tangle consisting of a single strand with a rotating twist or loop of the size of the wavelength, reproduces *all* observations about light quanta. This includes Maxwell's equations, classical optics, and quantum electrodynamics, as explained elsewhere [32].

In particular, the photon tangle explains the invariance and the limit property of the speed of light c , as well as its unattainability for systems with positive mass. Because of this invariance, special relativity follows from the strand tangle model, including the relativistic energy-momentum relation $E^2 = p^2 c^2 + m^2 c^4$. Also photon spin, countability, interference, and entanglement follow from strands. Any deviation or contrasting observation would immediately invalidate the strand tangle model.

17 Deducing decoherence and quantum measurements avoiding local hidden variables

In nature, all measurements and observations are both *quantum mechanical* and *electromagnetic*. In addition, whenever an experiment tries to measure or resolve action values of the order of the

quantum of action, *random*, i.e., *probabilistic* outcomes are observed. Whenever this happens, in addition to a random measurement result, measurements *collapse* the state of the system being measured to the corresponding eigenstate. This occurs following *Born's rule*, thus with a probability given by the squared magnitude of the coefficient of the eigenstate in the initial state of the system being measured. Experiments show that *no* hidden and non-contextual (i.e., local) variables determine or influence the measurement probabilities [102, 103]. Every measurement outcome is produced and recorded by a measurement apparatus that contains a bath – to store results – and that interacts with the system being measured [104].

Definition 86: A *bath* is a system described by a temperature, thus an irreversible system consisting of many particles.

Definition 87: A *measurement apparatus* is a device interacting with a physical system in such a way that it *projects* a quantum state onto specific base states and *stores* the result. A measurement apparatus is thus *specified* by an interaction that dissolves specified addition regions in superpositions and by a bath that stores the resulting base state and its properties.

The memory necessary for a measurement, and thus the bath necessary in every measurement apparatus, is necessary to erase the starting state of the measurement apparatus, and to store and to display the measurement result. The realization that storage requires irreversible processes and thus increases entropy is well-known [105]. The bath and the memory are often combined in the statement that measurement apparatuses have *classical* properties.

The strand model proposes a visualization of measurements that appears to reproduce all their observed properties. Because all observations are composed of crossing switches, the starting point of the strand description is

Statement 88: Physical observables consist of specific arrangements of crossing switches.

In simple words, physical observables are *composed* of crossing switches. Every measurement of a physical observable detects the corresponding arrangement of crossing switches. For example, detecting an electron implies detecting the effects of its electric charge, i.e., the effects of its three chiral core crossings. Likewise, detecting a photon implies detecting its rotating looped core. As another example, measuring momentum implies counting crossing switches per length. In contrast, observing just a *single* crossing switch only implies that *something* has changed, i.e., that some event occurred. Strands thus imply

Statement 89: Every measurement is quantum mechanical.

All measurements confirm this statement. In particular, all SI base units of measurement are based on quantum effects. But strands tell more.

In the strand tangle model, a *photon* consists of a strand with a rotating loop, as pictured in Figure 14 and explained in Section 16. The coupling between crossing switches and photons, illustrated in Figure 11, shows that every crossing switch has electromagnetic effects. Therefore, every crossing switch is *observable*. The fundamental principle thus *explains* the observability of crossing switches, despite the unobservability of strands. Above all, strands imply

Statement 90: Every measurement uses electromagnetism.

All observations agree. Again, the definitions of all SI base units confirm the statement. A provocative way to state the result of the strand model is:

Statement 91: Every measurement counts photons, be they real or virtual.

In particular, the above arguments and Figure 11 yield

Statement 92: Every measurement counts crossing switches.

For example, the strand model implies:

Statement 93: *Length* is the maximum number of crossing switches between two points.

Statement 94: *Time* is the maximum number of crossing switches between two instants.

Statement 95: *Energy* is the number of crossing switches per time.

Statement 96: *Momentum* is the number of crossing switches per length.

Statement 97: *Angular momentum* is the number of crossing switches per angle or rotation.

Statement 98: *Light intensity* is the number per time of crossing switches due to photons.

The list can be straightforwardly extended to other observables. As shown elsewhere [31–33], crossing switches also determine observable quantities not explained so far, such as the gauge fields and their coupling constants. In particular, the geometry of the coupling to electromagnetism illustrated in Figure 11 determines the value of the fine-structure constant and its running, because the geometry determines the probability of the coupling between a photon and a crossing switch [32].

The strand fluctuations in any quantum system and the fluctuations of the bath contained in every measurement apparatus also imply

Statement 99: Strands lead to *random* measurement outcomes.

Such probabilistic measurement outcomes are indeed observed in all experiments.

In nature, probabilities arise in measurements because every measurement apparatus, through its construction, uses the coupling to a bath and to its fluctuations to *project* the measured state to one of the possible eigenstates [106–111]. The design and construction of the measurement apparatus define the possible eigenstates. In the strand tangle model, an *eigenstate* is characterized by a specific core position, core size, core shape, core orientation or phase, and core dynamics [31]. The bath strands determine the specific measurement outcome by projecting the quantum state, i.e., by *deforming* the corresponding tangle into one of the possible eigenstates. This occurs by *dissolving the untangled addition regions*. This dissolution occurs strand segment by strand segment; each strand segment of the quantum system is pushed, or *buffeted*, by a strand segment of the bath. A visualization of the buffeting for the case of photon interference is given in Figure 37. The large number of bath strands makes the dissolution of the addition region irreversible. The result of the dissolution is random and depends on the fluctuations of all the involved strands. The deformation process of the system tangle during measurement – the projection onto an eigenstate by dissolution of the addition region – has two names:

Definition 100: The projection by dissolution of the addition region, i.e., by the shrinking of the tangle core, is called the *decoherence* process or the *collapse* of the wave function.

In the strand model, the many strands of the detector push or *buffet* the various curved regions of a superposition towards a single eigenstate. In simple words, the *buffeting* by the strands of the bath leads to collapse, projection, and decoherence. A video that visualizes the collapse using a tightening knot instead of a tightening tangle, though without the buffeting, is found at reference [112]. This process yields

Three snapshots of a spinning outer electron around a silver core entering and leaving a Stern-Gerlach magnet by moving away from the reader along the line of sight.

The final state depends on the details of the strand fluctuations of field and electron during the dissolution of the addition region.

Figure 36: The figure shows the spinning outer electron of a silver atom moving along the direction of sight towards a Stern-Gerlach set-up, moving inside it, and moving behind it. The inhomogeneous magnetic field defines the direction of spin measurement. The intermediate situation inside the magnet is that illustrated in Figure 21. As mentioned, a fascinating animation of this intermediate situation, by Jason Hise, is found at [youtube.com/shorts/-KGW3QvwFuE](https://www.youtube.com/shorts/-KGW3QvwFuE). To keep the picture simple, the strands of the magnetic field that produce the selection between ‘up’ and ‘down’ are not drawn.

Statement 101: Strands imply that decoherence occurs via *buffeting* by bath strands and selects a single measurement outcome.

Strand-induced decoherence dissolves addition regions. This yields a projection of the quantum state onto an eigenstate. As argued by Shaghaghi [46, 47], the existence of such projections, combined with the conservation of probability, leads to Born’s rule for wave function collapse. We suggest that once the arguments just given are made precise, one gets

Statement 102: Strands reproduce Born’s rule.

Strands describe measurement apparatuses with their thermodynamic properties. The thermal

Figure 37: The detection of a photon arriving at a screen after a double slit experiment is illustrated. The state is a superposition consisting of partial photons located at the dotted circles. The unobservable tethers of the bath in the detector *decohere* or *collapse* the superposition by shrinking the photon core by *buffeting* its curved strand segments to a localized eigenstate. The localized crossing switch of the photon is then detected.

de Broglie length describing the buffeting bath in the apparatus yields

Statement 103: Strands imply that decoherence takes a finite time.

The strand model thus implies that the decoherence time depends on the properties of the bath. Usually, the decoherence time is extremely short, usually unmeasurably so [113]. However, the decoherence time can be measured in dedicated experiments, such as those in quantum computing [114].

As an example, in nature, *measuring the spin orientation of a silver atom* in an initial quantum state with a definite spin orientation yields a final state of that orientation with a probability that depends on the relative angle between the the initial spin orientation and the spin measurement direction. This process occurs in the experiment by Stern and Gerlach, which is illustrated in Figure 36. For a *vanishing* relative angle, the result of a spin measurement is always the same, e.g., always ‘spin up’, and the final state is always the same as the initial state. In contrast, for a

relative angle of $\pi/2$, the spin measurement result is observed to be either ‘spin up’ or ‘spin down’, each with 50% probability. Strands reproduce all these observations. For a vanishing relative angle, the spinning tangle orientation remains unchanged. For the orthogonal case, because of the strand fluctuations, more precisely, because of the *buffeting* by the strands in the bath contained in the measurement apparatus, the measurement changes the spin orientation to either ‘up’ or ‘down’. (See Figure 37 for an illustration of the buffeting process.) In this specific case, the bath fluctuations are those of the magnetic field. The spin change occurs because a Stern-Gerlach apparatus only allows two opposite orientations as outcomes. The strands of the magnetic field bath dissolve the addition region of the state of the incoming atom. The randomness of the result is due to the randomness of the atom strand fluctuations and to the randomness of the buffeting of the bath strands forming in the magnetic field. The resulting probability depends on the relative angle between spin and magnetic field, as is observed.

The decoherence process can be visualized most easily for the position measurement of photons. *Measurements of particle position* imply that the complete tangle core, with all its topology, is detected in a specific region of space. A position measurement process is due to the bath strands pushing the complete tangle core towards a single detection region. For example, this happens on a photon scintillation screen, as illustrated in Figure 37. To detect a photon, the screen requires the presence of the *complete* core in one small region of space. A photon core that is spread out over a large region has a finite probability of being localized in any small region of space. During a measurement, the bath in the detector, with all its buffeting tethers, collapses the spread-out particle state into a specific small detection region. The collapse thus corresponds to the *contraction* of the spread-out tangle core into a small region of space, i.e., into a position eigenstate. The statistical bath properties imply the random result of the collapse, as usual in decoherence [113]. The probability of particle detection in a specific region depends on the probability density in that region. The collapse does not transport energy and thus is not limited by the speed of light. Above all, the large number of strands in the measuring bath implies that the photon tangle core *must* become localized, because the many bath strands pushing onto the spread-out photon core lead to the dissolution of the addition regions and to the localization of the photon core in one of the regions of constructive interference. The localization probability is highest for interference regions with the highest partial core content. In this way, measuring particle position therefore realizes Born’s rule. Again, the localization, i.e., the collapse or decoherence, takes time. The time is determined by the bath properties, as usual in decoherence [113]. Bath strands, with their collective buffeting, thus explain the appearance, spot by spot, of the interference pattern on a screen. In particular, the strand description confirms that interference experiments also work with single photons, as is observed [115].

All these properties and processes can be summarized with

Statement 104: Strands imply the lack of measurable deviations from decoherence.

This conclusion agrees with all observations [116]. Because strands are unobservable by definition, they give the impression of being *hidden variables*. Indeed, strands are unobservable by definition: strand shapes are *hidden*. But for the same reason, strand shapes are *not* variables. Only crossing switches are observables and variables. In addition, because the bath coupled to a quantum system determines the measurement outcome, strands are *contextual*. This yields

Statement 105: Strands realize the Kochen-Specker theorem that excludes *non-contextual hidden variables* [102].

In particular, due to the bath, to the ever-present fluctuations, to the unobservability of strands, and to the extension of strands, strands do *not* provide *local hidden variables*. Strands thus realize Bell's theorem [103], in agreement with observations. Alternatively, it could be argued that strands realize the well-known loopholes in Bell's theorem [117, 118].

Given that empty space also contains fluctuating strands, it *can* act as a bath. This occurs in all situations when empty space is described by a temperature, thus in all situations where it is curved, i.e., whenever gravity is involved, or in situations that contain a potential. In contrast, flat empty space without any potential does not act as a bath.

In Feynman's path integral formulation, point-like particle tangles trigger the detector. Also in this formulation, there is no difference between the conventional and the strand description.

Strands lead to additional mathematical consequences about measurements. As told throughout this text, space is 3-dimensional and its rotations form $SO(3)$. The group is not simply connected. Its universal cover is $SU(2)$, the 3-sphere, i.e., the unit quaternions. Physical states live on the cover, not the base. Observation probes relations in physical space, i.e., in $SO(3)$. Hence, observations necessarily collapse the underlying $SU(2)$ structure to $SO(3)$ data. The collapse is discrete because the cover is discrete. This yields

Statement 106: Measurement is the detection of a sheet transition in the double cover of $SO(3)$.

Statement 107: Crossing switches change the visible into the invisible.

Statement 108: The difference between invisibility and visibility is not metaphysical but topological.

Statement 109: Quantum theory is what happens if one takes topology seriously.

The strand model enables the future exploration of further aspects of quantum measurements. In many experiments, the *environment* plays an important role. Whenever the environment contains a bath, it has effects similar to those of a measurement apparatus just described, and leads to decoherence. Another aspect is that strands appear to put aside the idea of "*many worlds*". Instead, strands appear to confirm the analysis of quantum measurements by Zurek [107–109]. These and other topics merit further investigation.

In short, this section argued that the *fundamental principle* associating \hbar to a crossing switch and the *buffeting* by the fluctuating strands in the bath contained in every measurement apparatus yield the appearance of randomness in measurements, the occurrence of a single measurement result, the collapse of wave functions, the projection on base states defined by the construction of the measurement apparatus via decoherence that requires time, the storage of the measurement result, and, above all, Born's rule. Fluctuating strands do *not* provide non-contextual hidden variables, predict the lack of such effects, and respect causality. In contrast, because strands are unobservable, extended, fluctuating, and form empty space and baths, strands are *hidden*, but are also *contextual* and are *not variables*. All observables and measurement results are composed of crossing switches. Crossing switches are the conceptual bridge leading from the unobservable continuous to the observable discrete. Strands thus *visualize* the measurement process. Fluctuating strands do not differentiate between quantum evolution and the measurement process. In particu-

Figure 38: The fuzzy Dirac *spinor* wave function for an electron in a hydrogen 1s orbital emerges from its fluctuating tangle via its fluctuating crossings. The precession of the electron spin axis around the central proton spin is illustrated.

lar, fluctuating strands confirm that all measurements are based on quantum effects and make use of electromagnetism. Any contrasting observation, at any energy, would immediately invalidate the strand tangle model.

18 Deducing spinors, antiparticles, and the Dirac equation

The wave function was defined as the oriented crossing density of a rotating particle tangle in Section 7. The description led to the Schrödinger equation, which was deduced in Section 10 and Section 11. To deduce the Dirac equation requires taking into account length contraction, time dilation, and the additional angles β , γ , and δ that appear in strand crossings and that are illustrated in Figure 18 and Figure 19. These additional angles enable the description of spin $\hbar/2$ and of antiparticles. By incorporating these aspects, tangles of strands visualize the Dirac equation. This section *summarizes* the results derived elsewhere [12, 31, 35].

It is well known that the Dirac equation in *one* spatial dimension can be deduced from a discrete space-time, as Kauffman and colleagues have shown [119–121]. This is possible because in one dimension, \hbar and c are the only constants that play a role in the Dirac equation, and no effects of spin can be observed. In contrast, crossing switches of strands appear to be the only way to generalize these results to *three* spatial dimensions. In particular, crossing switches of strands appear to provide the only way to include spin, relativistic effects, and antiparticles into a quantum description.

A. By including, in the description of the wave function, the two angles β and γ shown in Figure 18 and Figure 19, one includes the *spin orientation* that was neglected in the Schrödinger equation, and thus includes the description of spin $\hbar/2$. In the non-relativistic domain, the angles allow defining a Pauli spinor ψ as

$$\psi = R e^{i\alpha/2} \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\beta/2) e^{i\gamma/2} \\ i \sin(\beta/2) e^{-i\gamma/2} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (15)$$

As before, all quantities depend on space and time and are averaged over a few Planck times. As before, the quantity $R = R(x, t)$ is the crossing density. As before, the half angles in the relation are due to Dirac's trick: *tethers* reproduce spinor behavior and the behavior of the unit quaternions. Pauli's spin algebra is the algebra of the unit quaternions. Strands thus incorporate the description of spin $\hbar/2$ into wave functions by taking into account the angles describing the *orientation* of crossings. This effectively implies adding a little flagpole, flag, and a sign at each crossing, thus yielding the well-known flag visualization of spinors [10, 122]. The tethers of each particle tangle naturally introduce a sign describing the tether entanglement and thus indeed yield complete spinor behavior. Using this generalized description of the wave function ψ , one gets the free, non-relativistic *Pauli equation* for the wave function of spin $\hbar/2$ particles [31]. In other terms, Pauli spinors are described by oriented crossing densities.

B. By including *relativistic effects* into the deduction of the Schrödinger equation from tethered rotation, Battey-Pratt and Racey deduced the *Klein-Gordon equation* that arises when spin is neglected, but when relativistic effects are taken into account [12]. They achieved this by including length contraction and time dilation into Dirac's trick. As usual, these relativistic effects are described by three boost parameters corresponding to the three linearly independent spatial directions. In the strand tangle model, boosts correspond to *squashing* the tangle core and the Dirac trick, as well as *changing their frequency*, both as described by length contraction and time dilation. In other words, the relativistic boost parameters describe how the spatial distribution of the crossings is changed by the particle speed.

C. The strand tangle model automatically leads to

Definition 110: *Antiparticles* are mirror tangles rotating in the opposite sense.

Therefore, antiparticles have the same mass and opposite charge. By including the remaining angle δ from Figure 19, antiparticles are included in the strand description. The transition to antiparticles occurs by *inverting the braiding* of the strands. This process is described locally by changing the angle δ from less than $\pi/2$ to more. Such a smooth transition to the mirror tangle is only possible for *rational* 3d tangles; in contrast, knots and links do not provide this possibility. By including this transition, tangles include an aspect that was missing in the work by Battey-Pratt and Racey.

Once all three just-mentioned aspects are taken into account in the description of the wave function as an oriented crossing density, the complete relativistic Dirac spinor wave function for particles and antiparticles is described by *one* amplitude, *four* angles and *three* boost parameters. Following the work by Hanson and Regge [123], Barut and Zanghi [124], Loinger and Sparzani [125], and Baylis et al. [126] about or inspired by relativistic tops, these eight parameters describe a relativistic spinor wave function as

$$\psi = R e^{i\delta} \mathbf{L}(\mathbf{v}) \mathbf{D}(\alpha/2, \beta/2, \gamma/2) . \quad (16)$$

In the expression, R is the crossing density, δ is the parameter describing the transition from particle to antiparticle, \mathbf{L} is a 4×4 matrix describing the boost transformation as a function of the real velocity vector \mathbf{v} , and \mathbf{D} a 4×4 matrix function of three real parameters describing the orientation and phase of the spin (or flag). Describing the complete spinor wave function thus requires one real number and seven angles. Figure 38 illustrates spin and precession resulting from the three angles α , β , and γ in the lowest state of a hydrogen atom. The angles determine the

orientation of the flag pole and of the flag representing the electron spinor wave function spinning and precessing around the proton spin.

Conventionally, the spinor wave function ψ with its eight parameters is written as a single-column matrix with four complex numbers with specific Lorentz transformation properties. A similar description has been given by Hestenes [127], who describes the geometry of the motion of spin $\hbar/2$ particles, though without tangles. In simple words, expression (16) implies that a Dirac spinor wave function is given, like all simpler wave functions, by the *oriented crossing density* of a rotating particle tangle. The description (16) of Dirac spinor wave functions leads to the free Dirac's equation in at least five ways.

I. In their paper [12], Battey-Pratt and Racey derived the free Dirac equation from a moving and rotating tethered particle model by including the relativistic aspects of Dirac's trick. The strand tangle model incorporates their approach and thus leads to the Dirac equation in the same way. Due to the chirality of fermion tangles, the dynamics of a spin $\hbar/2$ particle in a vacuum can be visualized as that of a tethered pinwheel or tethered maple seed, as in the Schrödinger case. But in addition, rational tangles include spin orientation, relativistic effects, and antiparticles.

II. The Dirac equation can be derived from strands in a further way. In the strand tangle model of fermion motion as a continuous series of Dirac tricks, the *spin current* is conserved. Following Lerner [128], the two conditions of spin current conservation and of Lorentz covariance completely and uniquely imply the Dirac equation for a spin $\hbar/2$ particle. Since the two conditions apply to the strand tangle model, the Dirac equation follows from strands [31].

III. The Dirac equation can also be derived, like the Schrödinger equation, from the path integral formulation [31]. This connection is illustrated qualitatively in Figure 27. Adding spin and relativistic effects does not change the illustration.

IV. The Dirac equation can also be derived from the principle of least action, which is explored and deduced from strands in the next section.

V. Strands also visualize Dirac's own derivation of his equation. Dirac was searching for the square root of the relation $\hat{E}^2 = \hat{\mathbf{p}}^2 + m^2c^4$ that is central to special relativity and to the Klein-Gordon equation, in order to get a linear relation. Tangles explain why this is possible. A quantum state for a massive spin $\hbar/2$ particle with a precise energy-momentum is, geometrically speaking, a rotating, advancing strand helix that includes spin. (In the case of fermions, this includes that the spin rotation axis is *not* aligned with the direction of motion, but precesses around it.) For such a helical state with a given energy-momentum, the energy operator \hat{E} *scales* and *rotates* the helix without shifting its position in space. In contrast, the momentum operator \hat{p} *scales* the helix diameter and changes the spin orientation. As a consequence, the two operators must be related by $\hat{E} = \mathbf{A}\hat{\mathbf{p}} + Bm$, where A_x, A_y, A_z , and B are complex matrices that describe the behavior of the spin rotation axis. Because these matrices describe spin, they are related to the unit quaternions and to the Dirac trick. The matrices are usually fixed by requiring, as Dirac did, that the energy-momentum relation be compatible with the Klein-Gordon equation, i.e., that $\hat{E}^2 = \hat{\mathbf{p}}^2 + m^2c^4$. This implies that 1, A_x, A_y, A_z, B , and their products form the so-called *Dirac algebra*, a special case of a Clifford algebra of 4 by 4 complex matrices [18]. The Dirac algebra is an extension of two copies of the Pauli spin algebra describing spinning particles and spinning antiparticles [31, 36]. Each Pauli algebra arises because tethers produce spin $\hbar/2$ and $SU(2)$ behavior. Thus, each Pauli algebra behaves like the unit quaternions, as told by Battey-Pratt and Racey [12]. Each

Pauli algebra is described by a set of 2 by 2 complex matrices. The Pauli matrices can be deduced from pairs of tethers [36], e.g., by exploring the details of Figure 9. The Dirac algebra arises once *two* such Pauli algebras, one for particles and one for antiparticles, are generalized by including a continuous transition, described by the angle δ mentioned above, between rational particle tangles and rational antiparticle tangles.

The derivations of the free Dirac equation from strands and their fundamental principle allow several conclusions. Because the strand model also derives spinor states, Hilbert spaces, and self-adjoint operators, strands of negligible radius also reproduce the Dirac-von Neumann axioms of quantum theory. Strands thus completely confirm quantum theory. And they yield more.

The Dirac equation takes into account the *complete* geometry of the crossings in an electron tangle that was visualized in Figure 19: *all* angles are taken into account. In contrast, the Schrödinger equation for a single electron takes into account only *a part* of the geometry of the crossings: only one angle is included. This explains why the Dirac equation is a more precise description of a single electron. Because the Dirac equation takes into account *all* angles arising in crossings, strands also *exclude* a more accurate description for a single electron than the Dirac equation – once the electromagnetic potential is included. The many-particle effects due to higher-order loops leading to quantum electrodynamics also follow from strands [32].

The Dirac equation takes into account spin, with its direction and precession, and all relativistic effects. In the case of the hydrogen atom, for example, the tangle shapes in the orbitals illustrated in Figure 28 must be amended. The electron tangle in the 1s state is not, on average, positioned with complete spherical symmetry around the proton; its spin is partially aligned with the proton spin. For the 2p state, the effects of special relativity on the tangle have to be taken into account. So far, no complete visualization of solutions to the Dirac equation in hydrogen has been published because of the difficulty in visualizing the four complex parameters of Dirac spinors. Starting from Figure 38, tangles promise to provide such visualizations as skeletons of Dirac spinors.

In short, this section *summarized* that the free Dirac equation arises once \hbar is identified with a crossing switch of unobservable strands and spinor wave functions are described as oriented crossing densities of propagating and rotating non-trivial rational 3d tangles [31]. The free Dirac equation arises because rational 3d tangles describe spin $\hbar/2$ particles, yield a smooth transition from particles to antiparticles, and because the Dirac trick is consistent with special relativity. This yields

Statement 111: Dirac's equation follows from Dirac's trick.

This result was first proven by Battey-Pratt and Racey in 1980 [12]. Strands predict that, for a single electron, no deviations from the free Dirac equation can be observed. Only virtual multi-particle effects from quantum field theory are predicted to affect observations for single electrons [32]. Any contrasting observation would immediately invalidate the strand tangle model.

19 Deducing the principle of least action from strands

In nature, all motion – that of particles and that of spatial curvature – follows the *principle of least action*. The principle of least action provides the basis for quantum mechanics, for the standard model of particle physics, and for general relativity. In particular, the Schrödinger equation and

the Dirac equation follow from and imply the principle of least action. In nature, action is the observable that measures the change occurring in a system. In microscopic systems for short enough times, action is not maximized or stationary, but is *minimized* [129]. Bertrand Russell called the principle the “law of cosmic laziness” [130].

Because the quantum of action is the measurement unit of action, in microscopic systems, nature keeps the number of action quanta as small as possible. For strands, this yields

Statement 112: The principle of least action is *the principle of fewest crossing switches*.

Because crossing switches are events, one gets

Statement 113: The principle of least action is *the principle of fewest events*.

In this way, strands provide a microscopic *description* of least action. But strands provide more.

As explained in Section 17, our senses and all measurement apparatuses show that all observations make use of electromagnetism. As shown in Section 16, the electromagnetic field is due to twists in single strands. With this connection, Figure 11 shows that all crossing switches *couple* to the electromagnetic field. Crossing switches thus imply an ‘effect’ or an ‘effort’. This connection is the reason that crossing switches imply an action: action is the physical quantity that measures the magnitude of change, of effects, or of efforts. In microscopic motion, nature keeps the necessary effect and the required effort as low as possible. Therefore, nature tries to keep the number of crossing switches as small as possible [31]. This yields the

Least Statement: Because nature tries to minimize the electromagnetic effects of crossing switches, strands *imply* and *explain* the principle of least action.

One can state that nature wants to generate as little attention as possible: *nature is modest*.

In short, this section argued that in the quantum domain, strands *describe* the principle of least action as the principle of the fewest crossing switches. In addition, when crossing switches are identified with \hbar and the strand description of electromagnetism is included, strands *explain* the principle of least action. This appears to be the first such explanation. Because the principle of least action implies the Dirac equation, strands confirm the result of Battey-Pratt and Racey in a further way. As a further consequence, strands predict the lack of observable deviations from least action. Discovering any contrasting observation would immediately invalidate the strand model.

20 Experimental tests of predictions deduced from crossing switches

In physics, mathematical descriptions must agree with *all* observations. The identification of crossing switches with \hbar can only be accepted if it fulfills this requirement.

- Strands predict that *no* deviations from the universal value of the quantum of action \hbar arise, at all measurable energies, and that *no* variations throughout the universe or over time do occur. So far, all observations confirm the constancy and invariance of \hbar [28, 29, 40]. Likewise, no deviation from the quantization of action or angular momentum has ever been observed.
- The topology of strand tangles predicts that *no* elementary particles with spin between 0 and $\hbar/2$ are possible, as Dirac explained [9]. Tangle topology also predicts that *no* elementary particles with spin $3\hbar/2$ are possible, but also that *no* elementary particles with non-standard statistics are

- possible. Tangle topology further predicts that massless fermions and massless particles with electric charge are *impossible* [31]. All these predictions agree with observations [40].
- The crossing switch defining \hbar implies the validity of the indeterminacy relation, without *any* exception [31]. The validity has been confirmed in all experiments so far. [40, 131].
 - Due to the fluctuations of strands, nature is fundamentally random. The probabilities that arise in nature are due to all other strands in the universe pushing each other. Due to the unobservability of strands and due to the definition of observables with the help of crossing switches, *no* effects due to non-contextual hidden variables are predicted to arise [31], neither in single-particle measurements nor in multi-particle entanglement experiments. Indeed, no deviations from the probabilities predicted by quantum theory have ever been observed [84, 86, 102, 103].
 - Strands predict that *no* measurable deviations from the free and linear single-particle Dirac equation or from perturbative quantum (field) theory occur, at all measurable energies. This prediction includes the non-linear effects explored by Weinberg [132], which were refuted because of their strange consequences [133, 134] and because of logical issues [135, 136]. So far, no deviations from the free and linear single-particle Dirac equation or from quantum (field) theory have ever been observed [40].
 - Strands predict that the principle of least action is valid in *all* measurable situations. This has been confirmed by all experiments, both in particle physics [40] and in general relativity [137].
 - Strands predict the lack of deviations from light speed invariance, from the known photon properties, and from quantum electrodynamics [32]. No such deviation has ever been observed [40].
 - In apparent contrast to standard quantum mechanics, strands predict an upper limit for the probability density given by the inverse cube of the minimum length, the diameter of the strands. Although this limit prevents the existence of delta distributions and of exact locality, the density limit cannot be reached in experiments. This unattainability is predicted for all relativistic quantum gravity limits – i.e., for all limits containing all three constants \hbar , c , and $4G$ [31, 67]. Because all relativistic quantum gravity limits are untestable in practice, strands predict the lack of measurable deviations from quantum field theory. So far, none has been observed [40].
 - In addition to predicting quantum mechanics, strands predict the lack of observable deviations from the standard model with massive neutrinos [32–36] and from general relativity, black hole thermodynamics, and conventional thermodynamics [59, 138–140], at all achievable energies, times, and locations throughout the universe. To date, despite potential counterexamples in galaxy dynamics, no deviation has been observed. The topic will be explored in Section 24.

In short, this and the previous sections showed that all observational evidence implies the

First Main Statement: Identifying the quantum of action \hbar with a crossing switch of unobservable strands reproduces *all* observations and all aspects of quantum mechanics, including the emergence of wave functions and the origin of the least action principle.

The description of the quantum of action \hbar with crossing switches thus appears to be *correct*. Observing any deviation between the strand tangle model and observations would immediately invalidate the strand tangle model – as would any direct observation of strands or tangles.

21 Alternatives to crossing switches

As shown so far, crossing switches model the quantum of action \hbar , imply all of quantum mechanics, and agree with all experiments. A literature search shows that *no* other model describes the quantum of action and its effects, despite various attempts, including those in references [21–27, 141]. Likewise, no model for \hbar has been used or proposed in the literature about emergent quantum theory, causal sets, loop quantum gravity, superstring theory, causal fermion systems, the octonion model, or any other approach to unification. The reason becomes clear when using the

Model definition 116: A *model* is a visualization *in* three-dimensional Euclidean space that uses countable *constituents* for space and particles that are *subsets* of 3d space.

The definition is a consequence of observation O1: nature is three-dimensional. This definition of a model allows the comparison of alternative models with the strand model for \hbar using crossing switches. The comparison is possible for each of the eleven points listed in Section 3.

1. In the strand tangle model, space consists of untangled unobservable strands, whereas particles are tangles of strands. Tangled strands are models for *spin* $\hbar/2$ and for *fermions*, as told in Section 5. Strands and their tangles thus form a model in the sense just defined.

In three spatial dimensions, *no* alternative constituent and *no* alternative model achieves the visualization and the explanation of spin $\hbar/2$ behavior, of fermion behavior, let alone of the spin-statistics theorem for spin $\hbar/2$ fermions. Neither the book by Duck and Sudarshan [38] achieves this, nor do the visualizations using the ball B^3 of Section 4 in which opposite points are identified. Also the coupled pendula presented by Leroy et al. [142, 143] or the sphere glowing in different colors constructed by Bernard-Bernardet et al. [144] fail to provide a model of spin $\hbar/2$ in the sense just defined. In particular, no model without tethers – and thus without extended constituents – reproduces the existence of a particle-independent smallest positive value for spin.

The existence of *countable* elementary particles of different types, including antiparticles and three fermion generations, is a challenge to any model proposal. Only a few models that explain the spectrum of elementary particles using extended constituents have ever been proposed. All these models are based on topology, such as the knot models by Ng [145, 146] or by Avrin [147], or the twisted ribbon model by Bilson-Thompson and colleagues [148–153]. (Substituting each ribbon with at least two strands yields a way to compare the ribbon model and the strand tangle model.) However, topological models for elementary particles face constraints [67]. Because of spin $\hbar/2$, particles must be tethered; they cannot be knots or links of finite size, but must be *tangles*. In addition, the particle transformations observed in decays and in particle reactions, including particle annihilations, exclude models of particles based on knotted tangles. Therefore, particles must be, topologically speaking, unknotted; they must be *rational* tangles. The classification of rational tangles yields that elementary particles can only consist of one, two, or three strands [31]. Tangles of four or more strands are composed of simpler tangles that can rotate independently. Elementary fermions of spin $\hbar/2$ can only consist of two or three strands tangled in a non-trivial way [31–35]. Elementary bosons of spin \hbar must be trivial tangles of *one* strand or *specific* tangles of *two* or *three* strands [36]. One elementary spin 0 boson is also possible [31].

In simple words, the *topology* of a tangle determines the spectrum of particles and their interactions [31–36], as summarized in Section 24. In particular this yields

Statement 117: No other model reproduces elementary particles, spin $\hbar/2$, quantum num-

bers, and fermion behavior.

However, it must be added that proving this uniqueness *independently of 3d space* remains a challenge.

2. In nature, the quantization of action and of angular momentum are consequences of discreteness. In nature, only extended objects can model discreteness. Quantization and discreteness are inextricably linked to extension. Extension, in turn, implies the importance of topology. In the strand tangle model, at the Planck scale, even though the discreteness of space and time is unobservable, the discreteness of action and angular momentum is due to three-dimensional topology, as shown by Dirac's trick. A literature search for other possible models, as defined above, yields

Statement 118: No other model apart from the strand tangle model explains the *quantization of angular momentum* and the *minimum action value* in measurements.

3. Section 7 defined *wave functions* as oriented crossing densities of fluctuating tangles. The description was deduced from the *geometry* of strand crossings in tangles. In the literature, no other model explains and visualizes complex wave functions. Likewise, no other type of constituent deduces deBroglie's wave-particle duality and the Schrödinger equation ab initio. Generally speaking, no alternative *model* for the emergence of quantum theory is available in the literature, despite numerous investigations [42, 154–167]. For example, fluctuating membranes do not reproduce quantum interference, and neither do fluctuating constituents that are Planck-sized or of finite size in all three dimensions [67]. This yields

Statement 119: Apart from oriented crossing densities, no other model for wave functions combines particle discreteness with wave-like, continuous probability densities.

4. Section 19 showed that strands *describe* quantum jumps and model them as *almost* discrete processes induced by photons at the Planck scale. It was shown in a separate paper [32] that the strand description of photons and their coupling to tangles reproduces quantum electrodynamics, including the g-factor of the electron. A literature search confirms

Statement 120: No alternative model for quantum jumps is currently known.

5. Strands explain and visualize the *non-commutativity* of quantum observables. In contrast, no visualization or model that uses non-emerging and completely continuous fields can yield non-commutativity together with countable particles and discrete action values. In particular, the non-commutativity of rotations and of particle exchange can only be modeled with topological structures consisting of *open* strands. In contrast, deformations of constituents *with ends, with branches, with knots, with finite size, with closed strands, or with membranes* are commutative. This yields

Statement 121: No model other than open strands without ends reproduces non-commutativity.

6. By confirming the maximum speed, the maximum force, and the quantum of action, experiments imply that there is a smallest measurable length and thus that space and particles are *fuzzy* at Planck scales. The surface dependence and the magnitude of black hole entropy imply that horizons are fuzzy and that they consist of countable fluctuating strands of Planck radius [138, 139]. Only fluctuating open strands without ends, without branches, without knots and without finite size lead to black hole entropy [67, 138, 139]. As told in the [Appendix](#), because black holes can form by collapsing particles, particles must also consist of fluctuating strands. The literature, in-

cluding that cited under point 3, provides no alternative emergent model for particles and quantum theory. The strand shape fluctuations thus lead to the *fuzziness* of quantum theory. This yields

Statement 122: Only fluctuating strands explain *Heisenberg's indeterminacy relation* and the *appearance of probabilities* in the quantum domain.

7. Visualizing quantum entanglement is an old dream. As discussed in Section 15, topological models based on closed strands do not reproduce all the observed properties of multi-particle entanglement. The same applies to *bit threads* [168–171] and to *partial entanglement entropy threads* [172]; these filiform constituents describe only selected aspects of entanglement and of relativistic quantum gravity. Apart from strands, no past approach provided a complete description of entanglement, of \hbar , or of the relation between them. This is due to the specific topology of strands and to their fundamental principle; only strands have a topology that allows multi-particle entanglement in complete agreement with observations. This yields

Statement 123: No model other than strands explains and visualizes quantum entanglement.

8. Strands model photons. A conceptually and topologically similar model for photons, the unpublished “schmoton” model, is found on the internet [173]. That model only lacks the identification of \hbar with a crossing switch. Despite numerous attempts, no other model accurately describes electromagnetic waves as composed of discrete photons. Also the various publications about “corkscrew” photons do not achieve this. This yields

Statement 124: No model other than strands can describe the countability of photons, their spin \hbar , their boson aspect, Feynman’s rotating arrow model [51], their U(1) gauge symmetry, their helicity, their parities, invariant speed, infinite lifetime, together with their wave properties such as wavelength, phase, interference, and Maxwell equations.

9. Modeling the probabilistic outcomes of *quantum measurements* with a partially discrete and partially continuous substructure that differs from strands but forms particles has not been successful. More precisely, non-contextual hidden variables are only eliminated by describing physical observables with observable crossing switches of unobservable strands. Specifically, only crossing switches reproduce Born’s rule, the collapse of the wave function [31], and decoherence. No other model for wave functions reproduces these processes. This is due to the unique combination of unobservable strands with observable configurations. This yields

Statement 125: Only observable crossing switches of unobservable strands eliminate hidden non-contextual variables.

10. Deducing the Dirac equation from deeper principles is challenging because of the difficulty of encoding spinor behavior and antiparticles. Apart from Battey-Pratt and Racey’s approach [12], several attempts to derive the Dirac equation from an underlying discreteness have been published [174–176]. But like the derivations based on spatial continuity [128, 177–182] and the extensive list of derivations given in [183], none of these other derivations enables *counting* particles in multi-particle states and *changing continuously* from particle to antiparticles. For example, *knotted* tangles prevent a smooth transition from a tangle to its mirror [67]. This yields

Statement 126: Only *rational* 3d tangles yield spinors, yield continuous transitions from particles to antiparticles, and deduce the Dirac equation ab initio.

11. Section 19 showed that strands *describe* the principle of least action as the principle of the

fewest crossing switches. A literature search shows that strands provide the *only* known description of the principle of least action. Furthermore, Section 19 showed that due to the coupling of crossing switches to electromagnetism, strands *explain* the principle of least action. The literature and the previous ten points lead to the following situation. First, no alternative model or visualization for the *quantum of action* \hbar is possible, and thus no alternative model or visualization of macroscopic action. Secondly, no alternative visualization, model, or explanation exists for the electromagnetic interaction and for *quantum measurements*. Thirdly, no alternative visualization, model, or explanation exists for the *minimization* of action, because no other model describes the effects and the observability of action quanta. This yields

Statement 127: No model other than strands explains the principle of least action.

These eleven arguments imply: no model other than the strand model for the quantum of action \hbar yields both emergent *continuous* wave functions and *discrete* many-particle behavior. Strands appear to be the only model that reproduces *wave-particle duality* and the *complementarity* of the quantum world. Other, inequivalent models are not possible. In principle, generalizing the above ‘model definition’ *might* yield an alternative model of the quantum of action \hbar . However, so far, no generalization or model has been published.

Strands are also unique for reasons beyond simple quantum mechanics. As told in Section 24, only strands deduce the complete Lagrangian of the standard model of particle physics with massive neutrinos and the Hilbert Lagrangian of general relativity.

In short, this section deduced the

Second Main Statement: No alternative, inequivalent model to crossing switches of strands explains, visualizes, or describes Planck’s quantum of action \hbar and quantum mechanics.

Thus, the fundamental principle modeling the quantum of action \hbar with crossing switches is *unique* and *compelling*, as Wheeler required in his essay [1]. In other words, *quantum theory implies that particles have tethers*. The assumptions are explored in the [Appendix](#). Finding an alternative, inequivalent model of quantum mechanics would immediately invalidate the strand tangle model.

22 Arguments against crossing switches

Despite the explanatory power and the agreement with observations, describing quantum theory with crossing switches of unobservable strands is not popular. There are several reasons.

- The evolution of strand *shapes* lacks a mathematical description. Although strands deduce evolution equations for crossing densities of strands, such as Schrödinger’s equation, as shown in Section 10 and Section 11, strands do *not* allow evolution equations for the strands themselves. Such a strand shape description, even though desirable, would contradict all experiments confirming the lack of hidden variables in nature and would contradict the unattainability of the Planck length. Nevertheless, in contrast to Feynman’s path integral description, strands visualize the motion of particles through space, visualize fermion behaviour, visualize the appearance of \hbar , and visualize masses and coupling constants, as shown in the next sections.
- The idea that a person walking into a room through one door and exiting through another *pulls* a huge number of tethers through the room is *unusual*. Indeed, one can only get used to this idea by recalling that all these tethers are untangled and unobservable, that the pulling requires

Figure 39: Top: *untangled* strand configurations form flat and curved three-dimensional space. Bottom: strand *weaves* form almost two-dimensional horizons, and rotating strand *tangles* form particles and wave functions. In all cases, observations and observables are due to crossing switches, whereas the tethering strands extending to or from the cosmological horizon remain unobservable.

no force, that untangled tethers form empty space, and that the untangled tethers pulled by the person cannot be distinguished from the tethers in empty space before the person entered.

- The description of physical space using strands instead of points *contradicts more than 2400 years of natural science*, when Zeno's arguments against the existence of the infinitely small were collectively brushed aside and continuous space consisting of points was introduced, as Euclid did in the first sentence of his *Elements*. Nevertheless, despite this ancient consensus, all experiments confirm the limit properties of \hbar , c , and $c^4/4G$. Therefore, all experiments imply that nature has a minimum length $\sqrt{4G\hbar/c^3}$ [67–79] and that the description of nature with points must be abandoned. Figure 39 illustrates the strand model for all observed physical systems. Only strands explain discrete particles of matter and light, the non-commutative aspects of the quantum world, the origin of wave functions, the existence of the smallest length, the entropy of black holes [138, 139], and the three dimensions of space. In other words, strands imply that every continuous observable is *emergent*. This includes fields, probability densities,

energy, curvature, length, and time. Every continuous physical observable arises by averaging configurations of crossing switches.

- Quantum theory and general relativity imply that nature consists of strands, thus of *unobservable* entities [31–36, 67, 138, 139]. This appears to contradict the requirement of observability and thus scientific principles. However, the contradiction is only apparent. Physicists are used to speaking about points in space, about point particles, and about wave functions, which are all unobservable. Like points, also strands are unobservable thinking tools used to describe nature. The fundamental principle implies that every crossing switch yields a specific observable effect, namely a quantum of action \hbar . As shown above, all physical observables are *unambiguously* defined with the help of crossing switches of unobservable strands. The description of nature with strands is thus *falsifiable*. In addition, Section 24 summarizes that the fundamental principle also allows deducing general relativity and particle physics in all their details. So far, the description of nature with strands thus agrees with *all* observations. Unobservable strands are thus acceptable as thinking tools because, like unobservable points or wave functions, the fundamental principle *unambiguously specifies* the procedure for deriving observables, for deriving observable consequences, and for deriving testable predictions, and because all these consequences and predictions *agree with all observations*.
- Besides unobservability, strands have further *uncommon properties*. In contrast to everyday ropes, strands cannot be cut and have no parts or constituents. (All statements to the contrary would contradict the lack of trans-Planckian observations and effects.) Strands are arbitrarily flexible, cannot produce or transfer tension, and have no fixed length. (Otherwise, additional interactions would exist, strands could be observed and would be hidden variables, and cosmology would not arise.) Strands are arbitrarily twistable and do not resist torsion: they resemble filiform indestructible clouds. Strands can move faster than light: they behave like images and not like particles. Strands have no mass and no quantum numbers: they are completely unobservable. Strands have *no* properties that enable following their motion: strands are not described by evolution equations. Thus, strands differ considerably from everyday ropes. Nevertheless, only strands with these uncommon properties reproduce Dirac's trick, yield the quantum of action, and lead to quantum theory. Only strands with these uncommon properties reproduce particle physics, black hole entropy, and general relativity, as argued in Section 24.
- The description of nature with strands is *counterintuitive*. Despite the popularization by Dirac, the suggestion that every particle is connected to the cosmological horizon appears almost unreasonable. Indeed, visualizing a hydrogen *atom* as an electron tangle orbiting a central proton tangle is not straightforward. However, Figure 4 and Figure 5, which visualize how two fermions can continuously orbit each other, help to get used to the description. Likewise, Figure 17 and Figure 28 help to visualize the orbitals of an electron in a hydrogen atom. Using these aids, visualizing atoms containing more electrons and more complex nuclei becomes possible. As stated in Section 5, tangles realize Pauli's exclusion principle and thus yield the usual electron shells and orbitals that make up atoms. Strands thus imply that heavier atoms are fascinatingly complex structures consisting of orbiting and spinning fermion tangles.
- Strands are *not axiomatic*: strands state that physical 3d space is due to untangled strands, but the fundamental principle has a continuous 3d space built in from the start. This circularity can be avoided only partially [31]. The space used in the fundamental principle is the local *background*

space introduced by the observer to describe observations. It is, effectively, a Euclidean space locally tangent to the physical space produced by the strands. Because, at the Planck scale, any unified description of nature must include the observer [31], the description with strands remains *circular* and the fundamental principle is *not* an axiom in the mathematical sense.

- In quantum physics, the idea that spin is rotation has often been *criticized* because no spinning spherical charge or mass distributions behaves like a spin $\hbar/2$ fermion. The description of spin as tethered *tangle* rotation avoids those criticisms. Strands clearly state that spin *is* rotation: Figure 3 and Figure 16 prove that tangle rotation can continue forever. Indeed, tangle rotation agrees with all observations; in particular it yields the same spin value also for different particle masses, as shown in the next section.
- The description of nature and quantum mechanics with strands might appear equivalent to the usual description and thus might appear a *useless* complication. This argument is refuted in the next two sections, where it is reported that strands explain interactions, with their gauge groups and coupling constants, and the spectrum of the elementary particles, with their quantum numbers, masses, and mixing angles. Without strands, all these observations remain unexplained.
- Strands could be *just a model* or *just a thinking tool* and not a description of nature's reality. Even though the previous section argued that no alternative to strands appears possible, the authors disagree on how to settle this issue, as told in the [Appendix](#). The answer is left to the reader.

In short, this section showed that the main criticisms about the strand model can be resolved. Any criticism that cannot be overcome would immediately falsify the strand model. Although strands are unobservable, strands enable *visualizing* and *explaining* quantum mechanics with its discrete, continuous, statistical, and measurement aspects. Strands thus help *understanding* quantum mechanics. Strands do so with a fundamental principle – describing the quantum of action \hbar with a crossing switch – that is *simple*. This fulfills one of Wheeler's requirements [1].

23 Beyond quantum mechanics 1: calculating elementary particle masses

As shown so far, observable crossing switches of unobservable strands deduce and reproduce quantum mechanics. This result alone would be uninteresting, were it not that strands enable going *beyond* quantum theory, once their *Planck radius* $\sqrt{G\hbar/c^3}$ is taken into account. Because the Planck radius includes the gravitational constant G , such strands enable determining the mass values of elementary particles *ab initio*.

In nature, twice the Planck length is both the minimum length and the minimum length measurement error [67, 68, 70, 71, 76–79], as explained in Section 13. Because of the minimum length measurement error, the strand diameter cannot be reached in any experiment [67]. This implies

Statement 129: Strands of Planck radius are *unobservable* – but not trans-Planckian.

Thus, Dirac's trick and all the results deduced so far for a negligible radius remain valid and remain compatible with observations for strands with Planck radius. Strands are smooth, i.e., infinitely differentiable, flexible tubes with Planck radius that do not self-intersect.

In nature, the *mass* of elementary particles connects the phase rotation frequency (energy) to the phase rotation wavelength (momentum). As mentioned, in the strand model, a fermion tangle core moving through the vacuum rotates. The model *assumes* that this happens in the same way

that a maple seed or a pinwheel rotates when falling through the air. In this description, the mass value describes the *pitch* of the tangle core and is due to the *average chiral shape* of the core. However, there are three differences: a fermion experiences no friction, a fermion is tethered, and the effective shape, or pitch, of a fermion depends on particle speed, yielding de Broglie's relation at low energy and the running of mass at high energy.

In the following, we *assume* that during the motion of a matter particle through the vacuum, three processes occur continuously. First, the chiral core is slowly rotating. In their paper, Battey-Pratt and Racey [12] did not consider vacuum strands or particle chirality. As a consequence, they did not derive the origin of particle rotation as a result of their motion through the vacuum. Because the chirality of elementary particle cores is *small*, a full core rotation takes many orders of magnitude longer than a crossing switch, which only takes about a Planck time. The second process occurring is a large number of rapid and wild tether fluctuations. The third process takes place only extremely *rarely*, and thus only after *many* strand fluctuations: typically after 10^{18} Planck times, the moving and rotating fermion tangle realizes Dirac's trick illustrated in Figure 3 and Figure 16. On the Planck scale, the Dirac trick takes place only *rarely*. Nevertheless, on our macroscopic scale, the Dirac trick occurs about 10^{25} times per second.

At present, there is no *precise* way to quantify the frequency of the core rotation, of tether fluctuations, and of Dirac's trick. Nevertheless, because Dirac's trick has a *low* probability on the Planck scale, all elementary fermion masses are predicted to be *much* smaller than the Planck mass. This yields the

Third Main Statement: Strands solve the *mass hierarchy problem* of particle physics.

This *might be* the first ab initio, i.e., the first Planck-scale solution to the hierarchy problem. Because, so far, only strands incorporate quantum theory, particle physics, and general relativity [31, 67], it *might be* that strands provide the *only* solution to the mass hierarchy problem.

Because the rotation time of particle cores is always larger than the minimum time, the strand model implies that the *total* energy of any elementary particle, including its kinetic energy, must always be lower than the Planck energy. Indeed, the Planck energy limit is not exceeded in any elementary particle observation, even in the most energetic cosmic rays known [184, 185].

Because mass is due to the (average) chiral shape of tangle cores, strands imply that particle masses are positive, uniquely fixed, not quantized, equal for particles and antiparticles, and constant throughout the universe. All this is observed [40, 186].

The relation between core chirality, mass, and electric charge due to the tangle model [31, 32] implies that every particle that is electrically charged must have mass. This is observed [40].

Despite all difficulties, the strand tangle model allows *estimating* mass values. The estimate is simplest for leptons. In nature, the six leptons – electron, muon, tau, and the respective neutrinos – are the only elementary fermions that occur as free particles and thus that move with Dirac's trick. In the strand tangle model, all leptons consist of three strands [31, 32, 34, 35]. The mass limit for leptons can be estimated directly from Figure 15 and Figure 16, which show the general rotation behavior of tangles with six tethers. During the propagation of a free lepton, the rotation of the central core and the Dirac trick occur continuously. This yields

Statement 131: *Lepton mass* is determined by the *probability per time* that the chiral tangle core has rotated twice *and* that its six tethers have performed Dirac's trick.

If a lepton would rotate *without* the Dirac trick, the tangled tethers would hinder its forward motion. Only the Dirac trick allows a lepton to *advance* through space. Dirac's trick of Figure 16 requires that the deformations of the six lepton tethers follow a specific sequence of intermediate configurations. The smallest number of necessary configuration steps yielding Dirac's trick is six, because at least three steps are needed for each core rotation, and because two core rotations are necessary for Dirac's trick. To reproduce Dirac's trick, all these configurations must occur in the correct sequence. In each configuration, the six tethers must have the correct distribution in space. Thus, the tethers must have, in each configuration, the correct permutation out of the $6!$ possible ones. This yields an estimate for the probability per time of Dirac's trick given by

$$m_{\text{lepton-strands}} < \left(\frac{1}{6!}\right)^{2 \cdot 3} \approx 7.2 \cdot 10^{-18} \approx 44 \text{ GeV}/c^2 . \quad (17)$$

Here, the maximum possible elementary particle mass, half the Planck mass $\sqrt{\hbar c/4G} = 0.61 \cdot 10^{19} \text{ GeV}/c^2$, was used as mass unit. The smallness of the value (17) highlights the importance of Dirac's trick. The value (17) is an *upper limit* for the mass of leptons because the additional processes necessary for the rotation of the core itself have been neglected. Those processes will slow down the rotation further and thus reduce the lepton mass value further. The measured mass value of the tau, the most massive of the leptons, is

$$m_{\tau} = 1.78(1) \text{ GeV}/c^2 . \quad (18)$$

The measured tau mass is thus about 25 times smaller than the estimated lepton mass limit. The difference arises because the effect of the chiral shape of the tau core was neglected.

An improved future mass calculation method must be valid for all six leptons and must consider core topology, core shape, core deformations, core precession, strand hopping, and the details of the Higgs mechanism. Quantifying these effects is a subject of research. In the strand tangle model, tangle complexity increases with each fermion generation [31–33]. At a given speed, more complex tangles rotate faster and thus imply higher mass values. Strands correctly deduce the observed mass sequences of charged leptons. Neutrinos, being electrically neutral, have especially simple cores with low chirality that rotate even less easily [31]. Strands thus imply especially small mass values for neutrinos. This is observed [40]. Strands also predict the *normal* ordering of neutrino masses [32]. Observations, though not conclusive, suggest the same [40]. More precise mass estimates are in work.

The strand tangle model also allows comparing the experimental value of the W boson mass

$$m_W = 80.4(1) \text{ GeV}/c^2 . \quad (19)$$

to strand estimates. Again, this requires estimating the probability of a W boson core rotation. The W boson core is triangular, yielding unit charge, and its three strands are aligned along one common axis, yielding spin $1\hbar$. [31–36]. Being a boson, the W core rotates like that of a photon, with the three strands forming a loop around the triangular core that rotates, without any Dirac trick. While a W boson advances, the triangular core rotates. In every W boson core rotation, each crossing must move towards the next crossing, taking the correct position and orientation. The

probability for this process can be estimated. Each core crossing can move in the correct direction or in one of many wrong ones. This is valid for each of the three coordinates and for each of the orientation axes. In a simple estimate, the correct direction is 1 out of $4^3 = 64$ possible ones. To realize the full core rotation, all three crossings must move three times to the correct position and orientation. The estimated probability per time is

$$m_{W\text{-strands}} \approx \frac{1}{(64^3)^3} \approx 5.6 \cdot 10^{-17} \approx 339 \text{ GeV}/c^2, \quad (20)$$

where the maximum elementary particle mass was again inserted. The estimate $1/64$ surely has an error of 30%. This implies a strand estimate for the W boson mass of

$$32 \text{ GeV}/c^2 < m_{W\text{-strands}} < 8.4 \text{ TeV}/c^2. \quad (21)$$

The estimated mass range is wide but contains the observed value. The W boson mass estimate differs from the electron mass estimate, which has a similar core, because the rotation processes differ. Also the Z boson mass can be estimated in this way, as shown in reference [31]. Deducing an improved estimate for weak boson masses and their running is a subject of research.

The Higgs boson has spin 0. When it advances through the vacuum, its core does not rotate, even though its phase does [31–36]. A mass estimate is also possible [31].

The lack of free quarks complicates the discussion of their mass values. This is a research subject. The strand model explains the lack of free quarks as a consequence of is due to their tetrahedral tether geometry and reproduces hadron mass sequences [33].

In nature, all elementary particle masses depend on the four-momentum. In the strand tangle model, this so-called *running* of particle masses is a consequence of the relativistic length contraction and time dilation at high particle energies. The qualitative details agree with observations [31]. Estimating the running from tangles more precisely is a subject of research.

In short, this section showed that the strand tangle model with strands of Planck radius explains why nature provides unique, small, and running mass values for elementary particles. Strands thus go *beyond* quantum mechanics. The mass values of free fermions are determined by the average shape of their chiral particle tangles that continuously rotate and perform Dirac’s trick when propagating through the vacuum strands. The low probability of Dirac’s trick and of boson rotation solves the *mass hierarchy problem* of particle physics. Particle mass is a relativistic quantum gravity effect due to the Planck radius of the strands in the particle tangles. First estimates of elementary particle masses are compatible with the observed values. Strands thus realize Wheeler’s dream to define “mass without mass” [187, 188]. Finding any different ab initio explanation of mass values or any future disagreement between improved strand mass calculations and experiment would immediately invalidate the strand tangle model.

24 Beyond quantum mechanics 2: particle physics, gravitation, cosmology

In nature, all observations are based on quantum effects. Therefore, strands and their fundamental principle must provide testable consequences and predictions for *all* observations, including all those *beyond* quantum mechanics. A summary of publications checking this requirement follows.

- Strands determine, via the *classification of rational tangles*, the spectrum of elementary bosons and the three generations of fermions, with their spins, charges, parities, and all other quantum numbers [31–36]. Strands predict the lack of additional elementary particles – also in dark matter. This agrees with observations [40]. Strands thus realize Wheeler’s dream to describe “elementary particles without elementary particles” [188].
- Strands determine, via the *classification of tangle deformations*, the three gauge interactions and their gauge groups. The Reidemeister theorem about the three possible deformation moves provides the classification [36]. The first Reidemeister move yields electromagnetism, the second Reidemeister move yields the weak nuclear interaction and its symmetry breaking, and the third Reidemeister move yields the strong nuclear interaction, each with its Lie group [31–33, 36]. Strands predict the lack of additional gauge groups in nature, at any energy. This is observed [40]. The connection between strands and Lie groups also recalls the relation between fourfold vertices and Lie algebras that is found when exploring the topology of graphs [15].
- Via the *first Reidemeister move*, strands determine the interaction between photons and electric charges, the origin of electric and magnetic fields, and the appearance of Maxwell’s equations [32]. The first Reidemeister move also determines the tangle of the photon. An electron is a topologically chiral, alternating tangle of three strands. This topological chirality yields, with its three crossings, a unit electric charge. Likewise, chiral crossings yield the fractional electric charges of the quarks [33]. Any electric charge leads to the emission and absorption of virtual photons, in the way illustrated in Figure 11. This coupling of chiral tangles to photons yields quantum electrodynamics in all its observed aspects, including minimal coupling, the repulsion between charges of the same sign, the lack of magnetic monopoles, the value of the fine-structure constant, and the anomalous g-factor [32]. Strands thus realize Wheeler’s dream to describe “electromagnetism without electromagnetism” and “charge without charge” [188].
- Strands determine, using the particle tangles and the Reidemeister moves, all *interaction vertices* that are possible in Feynman diagrams. The lack of deviations from the observed conservation laws is predicted. No observed vertex is missing. No vertex beyond those of the standard model with massive neutrinos and perturbative quantum gravity arises – and the lack of such additional vertices is predicted. The vertices yield all the terms of the Lagrangian of the standard model with massive Dirac neutrinos [31–36] – including quantum electrodynamics, quantum chromodynamics, and the weak interaction with the Higgs mechanism. Strands thus predict the lack of any measurable deviation from the Lagrangian of particle physics. This is observed [40].
- Strands of Planck radius explain the *uniqueness* and the *running* of particle masses, of gauge coupling constants, and of the mixing phases. These constants of nature result from the *average shape* of particle tangles. However, to date, numerical evaluations *remain rough* [31–33, 67], as shown in the previous section, and must still be improved. Strands *predict* the lack of measurable deviations from particle physics.
- Strands of Planck radius explain *physical space* and describe its fluctuations. Strands explain that *three-dimensional continuous flat* physical space emerges – at measurable distances much larger than the Planck length – as an approximation of many untangled strands [31, 138]. The three dimensions, with all their non-commutative aspects arising in rotations and in vector products, arise from strand topology. Strands also predict the lack of any observable deviation from three-dimensional, continuous space-time [67]. This is observed [137].

- Strands of Planck radius imply that *gravitons* exist but are unobservable individually. The twisted strands that arise and disappear around cores during Dirac’s trick, illustrated in Figure 3, are the *virtual* gravitons around any massive particle in flat space [138, 139]. Dirac’s trick thus models everyday gravity and its inverse square dependence as a result of virtual gravitons. Because both inertial and gravitational mass are due to Dirac’s trick, the equivalence principle follows and holds for all massive particles. This agrees with all observations [137].
- Strands explain curvature. Because the average untangled strand or tether shapes in empty space are geodesics, *curved* physical space is due to untangled strands of Planck radius that depart from one crossing and form a second crossing at a *macroscopic distance* [138]. This model of curvature, illustrated in Figure 39, predicts the lack of wormholes, time-like curves, cosmic strings, and non-trivial spatial topology. This agrees with all observations [137].
- Strands explain black holes. *Woven* strands of Planck radius form all black hole *horizons*. Using Figure 39, fluctuating strands explain black hole entropy, mass, and temperature [34, 35, 67, 138, 139]. Because of Jacobson’s argument [189], this allows deducing Einstein’s field equations of general relativity and their Hilbert Lagrangian [138, 139, 190]. Black hole rotation is explained as a Dirac trick for a system with a huge number of tethers. Because strands visualize both empty space and spin, they resolve the issue of combining the respective topological structures. Strands thus provide an approach to relativistic quantum gravity. In particular, strands predict the lack of any measurable deviation from general relativity and the lack of any new observable effect of pure relativistic quantum gravity. This is observed [137].
- In cosmology, strands imply that nature consists of just one or a few strands crisscrossing the universe and increasing in length and tangledness [31]. As a consequence, the universe is surrounded by an expanding cosmological horizon consisting of woven strands. Strands solve the flatness problem and the horizon problem, predict the lack of inflation, predict the lack of space, matter, and radiation beyond the cosmological horizon, and imply that there is *no* “wave function of the universe”, due to the lack of an environment [31, 138]. This does not contradict cosmological observations. Strands thus modify Wheeler’s 1940 phone call to Feynman that “all electrons are the same electron” into “all particles consist of the same tangled strand(s)”.
- For physics as a whole, strands predict the lack of observable effects beyond the standard model with massive neutrinos and beyond general relativity. At present, the only candidates for such effects are certain aspects of early cosmology as well as the rotation curves of galaxies, galaxy groups, and wide binaries. All these candidate effects are often explained by postulating *dark matter*. Strands exclude the existence of *elementary* dark matter. Instead, strands predict that dark matter, if it exists at all, is due to conventional particles and black holes. Indeed, recent research by Galoppo, Wiltshire, and Re [191] suggests that pure general relativity might explain most effects attributed to dark matter. A separate article will explain the nature of *dark energy* with strands.

In total, strands and their crossing switches appear to reproduce fundamental physics completely. In the research literature, numerous models of nature have been based on extended constituents. For example, filiform constituents that yield crossing switches by *passing through* each other – impossible for strands and tethers – are used in the exploration of virtual knots [192–194]. However, these approaches do not appear to yield gravitation or particle physics. Other approaches to relativistic quantum gravity use filiform constituents that cannot pass through each other [195–

204]. Several approaches [205–208] even avoid a fixed causal structure. These approaches yield three-dimensional physical space but do not deduce the standard model of particle physics. Twist-induced crossing switches of strands overcome this limitation. Because *only* filiform constituents appear to imply black hole entropy, the properties of flat and curved space, *and* the properties of particles, other constituents explaining gravity and particle physics appear excluded [67]. If confirmed, this exclusion strengthens the fundamental principle and its derivation of physics.

In short, this section *summarized* that the fundamental principle relating the quantum of action \hbar to a crossing switch of strands of Planck radius reproduces particle physics, general relativity, and cosmology. Strands yield a

Fourth Main Statement: Strands predict the lack of any measurable deviation from the Lagrangians of general relativity and of the standard model of particle physics with massive Dirac neutrinos.

Any observation of physics beyond the standard model with massive neutrinos or beyond general relativity, or any inequivalent model with the same explanatory power would immediately invalidate the strand tangle model. In particular, strands predict that no *new* relativistic quantum gravity effects are observable, and that the *only known* quantum gravity effects – elementary particle masses, coupling constants, mixing angles, and their running – are unique and calculable. Their values determine the colors in nature. The strand description of nature appears *beautiful*, as Wheeler required [1].

25 Beyond quantum mechanics 3: foundations

Strands have implications for the foundations of physics. First, as a consequence of strands, nature is a unity *without exact parts*. Dante can be seen as an early proponent of the approach: around 1320, in the last canto of his *Commedia*, he described the universe as a knot spread out all over nature. Indeed, all so-called ‘parts’ of nature – particles, points in space, instants in time – are low-energy *approximations*. The first mathematical proposal to describe nature by eliminating exact parts was by Kauffman [209, 210]. In this proposal, all sets and elements are approximate concepts resulting from topological configurations of a unique fundamental entity. The fundamental principle of the strand tangle model realizes this approach. As a consequence of the lack of parts, as mentioned in Section 22, an axiomatic description of nature as a whole, thus up to the Planck scale, is impossible [31]. As a further consequence, strands exclude the possibility of a unified equation [31]. Conversely, any alternative description of nature as a whole that is based on sets and elements, or that is completely axiomatic, or that goes beyond the fundamental principle, would immediately falsify the strand model. In the precise mathematical sense, the fundamental principle is *not an axiom*.

Strands highlight the lack of axioms in the issue of the origin of three-dimensionality. On the one hand, three dimensions are needed to talk about nature. On the other hand, the number of dimensions arises from strands, because only three dimensions allow tangled structures of filiform constituents. The circularity can be reduced [31], but it is unlikely that it can be fully resolved.

Tangles of strands also challenge mathematical knot theory. In nature, the knots and links made of *matter* that are observed [15], such as knots in ropes, knots in DNA, or knots in fluid vortices,

consist of interacting fermions. In the strand model, configurations of fermions are neither knotted nor linked. Even quantum entanglement, discussed above, produces no knots or links. In nature, also knotted or linked *field* configurations play a role, from knots in the gluon field to the Aharonov-Bohm effect. Such configurations consist of bosons. Again, the strand model implies that these configurations of bosons are neither knotted nor linked at the Planck scale. Strands thus imply that all macroscopic knots or links, be they made of matter or radiation, are *approximate*, and that mathematical knots and links do not exist at the Planck scale. The strand tangle model thus can be called the *theory of the unknot*. Any argument or experiment disproving the statement would immediately falsify the strand model.

The universe consists of one or a few strands, and all motion and all observations result from evolving strand configurations. Because strands cannot be cut, they are not made of parts or of a substance. Long ago, when Kelvin and Poynting described matter particles as knotted vortices in the aether, they attempted to abolish the idea that nature is made of parts. Strands realize the program by describing particles and the vacuum as made of unobservable strand segments of a *single* strand (or in a *few* strands) making up the universe [31]. During the evolution of the universe, the length and the tangledness of the universal strand or strands continuously increase. At present, it appears hopeless to try to count the universal strand(s).

In short, in the strand tangle model, nature has no parts and thus is not axiomatic. Strands thus overcome reductionism and allow stating: *every thing is made of everything*.

26 Conclusion and outlook

In summary, the fundamental principle – the topological description of Planck’s quantum of action \hbar as an observable crossing switch of unobservable strands of Planck radius – agrees with all observations: *Every quantum effect is due to crossing switches, and every crossing switch is a quantum effect*. When modeling quantum particles as rational 3d tangles of fluctuating strands, continuously rotating tangle cores performing Dirac’s trick visualize spin, fermion behavior, wave-particle duality, wave functions, and Feynman’s path integral formulation. Every rotation of a tangle core – using Dirac’s trick if it is a fermion tangle – produces crossing switches and thus leads to the appearance of \hbar in de Broglie’s relations. As a consequence, the quantum of action \hbar is central to quantum theory. Quantum theory arises when one takes topology seriously.

Describing the quantum of action \hbar as a crossing switch enables counting quantum particles and describing their indistinguishability, their spin values, and their fermion or boson behavior. Crossing switches and Dirac’s trick lead, for the first time, to the emergence of spinor wave functions as oriented crossing densities of non-trivial fermion tangles. Crossing switches and Dirac’s trick imply the Schrödinger and Dirac equations. Also for the first time, crossing switches model the continuous transition from particles to antiparticles and the principle of least action. Crossing switches model photons, with all their properties, as rotating strand loops. Crossing switches explain interference, superpositions, Hilbert spaces, Fock spaces, non-commutativity, probabilities, the indeterminacy relation, quantized angular momentum, entanglement, decoherence, and quantum measurements. No alternative description of \hbar consistent with observations appears possible.

Describing the quantum of action \hbar with a crossing switch and describing particles as rotating tangles goes *beyond* quantum mechanics: its open questions are answered. In particular, tangles

and the Dirac trick explain the observed appearance, for all elementary particles with topologically chiral tangles, of a fixed *mass value* that runs with energy. For the first time, a model solves the *mass hierarchy problem* by providing, ab initio, an upper limit for lepton masses near the correct magnitude. To date, no alternative approach achieved this. This yields the

Result: So far, *only* the description of \hbar with an observable crossing switch of unobservable strands of Planck radius *explains* wave functions, quantum mechanics, and quantum field theory, *explains* the standard model of particle physics with massive mixing Dirac neutrinos, *answers* its open questions, such as the mass hierarchy problem, and *predicts* the lack of physics beyond it.

Motion is a sequence of Dirac tricks. So far, all this agrees with all observations. Any disagreement would immediately invalidate the strand tangle model.

Dirac's trick for unobservable strands leads to quantum theory and models the virtual gravitons around particles. Dirac's trick thus yields inverse square gravity and implies the equivalence principle for particles and therefore for all matter and radiation. Fluctuating strands and Dirac's trick thus visualize how the vacuum, curvature, and spin are compatible, in particular, how spin and its topology are compatible with diffeomorphism invariance. For highly involved tangles, Dirac's trick also models black hole rotation. Because strands also yield and explain general relativity, including curved space and horizons, *all of nature appears to consist of unobservable strands of Planck radius with observable crossing switches. Nature appears to be simple.*

When Wheeler explored the question "How come the quantum?" [1], he asked:

The necessity of the quantum in the construction of existence: out of what deeper requirement does it arise? Behind it all is surely an idea so simple, so beautiful, so compelling that when – in a decade, a century, or a millennium – we grasp it, we will all say to each other, how could it have been otherwise? How could we have been so stupid for so long?

The fundamental principle arises from the relation between the quantum of action \hbar , non-commutativity, topology, and geometry. The *counterintuitive* definition of \hbar as a crossing switch of unobservable strands of Planck radius explains why this answer took so long to be found.

In the future, describing Planck's quantum of action \hbar with crossing switches will enable the exploration of many other questions about nature. In particular, the strand tangle model will be useful for teaching quantum theory: strands will allow animated visualizations of the motion of free electrons, of double slit interference, of gauge interactions, of electrons in atoms, of entanglement, and of the measurement process. Strands also allow exploring questions about qubits, perturbative quantum electrodynamics, nuclear interactions, quantum gravity, and cosmology. Above all, strands will allow more precise calculations of the particle masses, of the coupling constants, and of the other fundamental constants of nature. With these and other explorations, the above result of the strand tangle model should be tested further, thoroughly and relentlessly.

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Appendix: On the assumptions and the necessity of strands

The authors are not in complete agreement on the statements in this Appendix, which is therefore added to stimulate discussion and further investigation. The main text argued that *only* strands imply quantum theory and deduced this conclusion from the claim that *only* strands describe spin $\hbar/2$. What are the assumptions, and how compelling is the argument chain for such a claim? The claim that strands are *necessary* rests on two observations that form its two assumptions:

Observation O1: All change and all motion in nature is observed to consist of evolving *localized particles*, evolving *two-dimensional horizons*, and evolving *three-dimensional empty space*.

Observation O2: All change in physical systems is observed to be limited by a *minimum action* \hbar , a *maximum energy speed* c , a *maximum force* $c^4/4G$, and a *minimum system entropy* $k \ln 2$.

In numerous searches [40, 59, 66, 137, 190] and despite the promise of big rewards, no hint of a deviation from these two observations has ever been found. (We note that both assumptions are part of the fundamental principle.) Starting from these two assumptions, the argument chain for the necessity of strands [67] consists of several steps.

Step 1: Observations O1 and O2 *distinguish* elementary fermion rotations by one turn from those by two turns, and likewise, simple exchanges of two fermions from double exchanges.

Step 2: Because of observation O2, elementary fermions are observed to be smaller than their Compton wavelength. Because of observation O2, in contrast to the rotation of a ball or a planet, rotations of elementary fermions *cannot* be detected by following the motion of their geometric structure, shape, or surface features. In addition, because of observation O2, *partial* rotations of elementary fermions are unobservable.

Step 3: Observation O2 includes that fermions of *different* masses, wave functions, and chiralities are observed to have the *same* spin value $\hbar/2$. Therefore, in contrast to the rotation of a ball or a planet, the spin of fermions cannot be a geometric effect but must be a *topological* effect.

Step 4: Because of observations O1 and O2, *the effects of full rotations of elementary fermions are not only topological but are also always relative to the cosmological horizon, the black night sky*. Fermions are thus topologically *related* to the cosmological horizon and thus topologically *connected* to it. This is Newton's bucket argument for elementary fermions, or, if preferred, the fermion version of Mach's principle. The only remaining topological way to distinguish elementary fermion rotations – for observations, for measurements, and for nature itself – is by counting full rotations with respect to a distant environment using *Dirac's trick* (see also Section 21).

Step 5: Observations O1 and O2, together with the properties of horizons, imply that *black holes*

have an entropy of the order of the Bekenstein-Hawking expression. The existence of this black hole entropy implies that black holes are made of fluctuating constituents. The surface dependence of black hole entropy implies that the constituents are *filiform, without branches, without a finite length, without ends, without knots, and open* [67, 138, 139].

Step 6: The order of magnitude of black hole entropy implies that the fluctuating constituents of black holes and horizons have a projected cross-section given by the minimum area, four times the Planck area. The minimum area itself arises by combining the limits of observation O2.

Step 7: Black holes can be described both as compressed fermions and as curved space. Therefore, black holes, fermions, and space consist of *common* constituents [67]. Observations O1 and O2 imply that these constituents of nature occupy *subsets* of three-dimensional space. Therefore, black holes, horizons, fermions, and space consist of common, open, filiform constituents with minimum diameter, i.e., with Planck radius, reaching the cosmological horizon.

Step 8: Observation O2 also implies minimum length measurement errors. The minimum measurement errors imply that, in every measurement attempt, filiform constituents with Planck radius are intrinsically *unobservable* because nature *prevents* reaching any Planck-scale limit that is defined with *all three* quantities c , \hbar , and G . This contrasts with Planck limits containing just one or two of these constants [31, 67], which *can* be reached. Therefore, horizons, black holes, space, and particles consist of fluctuating, unobservable *strands* with Planck radius that reach the cosmological horizon.

Together, steps 1 to 8 yield the desired conclusion. *Only* fluctuating unobservable strands with Planck radius produce localized fermions of spin $\hbar/2$ with their wave functions and chirality, *and* produce two-dimensional horizons and black hole thermodynamics [138, 139], *and* produce the three dimensions of space, because three is the only dimension for which strands can form tangles. As a consequence, observations O1 and O2 lead to the fundamental principle of the strand model. Vice versa, only the fundamental principle of the strand model explains observations O1 and O2.

In short, there appears to be no *obvious* loophole in the arguments leading to the *necessity* of strands. Any loophole that cannot be overcome would immediately invalidate the strand tangle model. To avoid premature conclusions, the search for loopholes should continue.

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